

**DEVELOPMENT OF NOBLE METAL BY ELECTRODEPOSITION
METHOD AND THEIR APPLICATIONS**

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SYNOPSIS

1. TITLE: “DEVELOPMENT OF NOBLE METAL COATING BY ELECTRODEPOSITION METHOD AND THEIR APPLICATIONS”

2. INTRODUCTION:

Electrodeposition refers to a film growth process which involves in the formation of a metallic coating onto a base material occurring through the electrochemical reduction of metal ions from an electrolyte [1]. Various parameters like current density, pH, temperature, nature of the electrode, physical and chemical nature of substrate surface etc. are responsible for the good coating on the base metal.

Figure 1: Cell used for electrodeposition. Chepuri R.K. Rao et al., 2004)

Noble metals: In chemistry, the noble metals are resistant to corrosion and oxidation in moist air (unlike most base metals). Noble metals are widely used in petroleum, chemical, electronic, electrochemistry, electrical, marine and aviation industry, known as the industrial “vitamin” [2]. The Platinum Group Metals (PGM) comprise platinum, palladium, rhodium, ruthenium, iridium, and osmium. Of the six, only platinum, palladium, and rhodium have hitherto found significant application in the electrodeposited conditions [3]. Many electrolytic processes employ precious metal electrodes and, for reasons of cost, practical electrodes are normally a thin coating of the precious metal on an inert substrate [4]. The pioneering work on electrochemical deposition was done by Elkington more than 100 years ago in 1837 [6]. Electrochemical deposition of platinum is practiced from chloride, ammine, sulfate-nitrite and hydroxyl complex [5]. The most stable oxidation state of Rh is +3 which has a great tendency to form complex ions in aqueous solutions. Rh is used as a coating material on scientific, surgical instruments, contact materials in rf circuits [7]

Elemental composition of SS304	
Elements	SS304
Carbon	≤ 0.08
Manganese	≤ 2.00
Phosphorous	≤ 0.045
Sulfur	≤ 0.030
Silicon	≤ 1.00
Chromium	18.0-20.0
Nickel	8.00-10.50

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

An in-depth literature review was conducted, with the goal of understanding the definition of noble metals, electrodeposition, applications studied, dye degradations, hydrogen generation, and antibacterial studies and their effects on society. Furthermore, the aim is to bring focus to the research problem, improve methodology, broaden knowledge, and reinterpret results. Particular attention has been given to the development of noble metals like platinum and rhodium and their alloys on the SS304 substrate using a novel electrolytic bath composition without any brighteners or levelers. The literature also mentioned the scope and applications where our samples can be employed on a commercially large scale.

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH

By considering the concepts of electrodeposition of noble metals, characterization and their applications in photocatalytic dye degradation, production of hydrogen and antibacterial study, the objectives set forth for the study may be broadly stated below.

- Surface modification of stainless steel (SS304) by using noble metal electrodeposition.
- Optimizing the bath by specific parameters like applied potential, pulse on time, pulse off time, and additives in solution to order to get uniform and nanosized deposition.
- Characterization of the coatings by SEM, XRD, and AFM
- The work's success will be scaled up to bigger scales, as well as enhancements that are required.

5. METHODOLOGY OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH

- The main objective of the research is to develop optimized bath composition of noble metals, its characterization and their applications to the society such as photocatalytic dye degradation, generation of hydrogen, and mitigation of bacteria called an antibacterial agent.
- It is a patent-oriented type of research.
- Research problem is well defined and stated in the problem statement.

Various steps are involved in the research process,

1. Set up experimental procedure.
2. Preparation of solutions and selection of proper electrodes.
3. Optimization of the bath like adding various additives (Brighteners, levers, stress reliever etc), pH, temperature and current density adjustment in order to get uniform and nanoscale crystals on the substrate.
4. Characterization of the coatings by SEM, XRD, and AFM to study the surface morphology, chemical composition, elemental arrangements etc.
5. Study of coated samples for various applications such as dye degradation, hydrogen generation, and antibacterial studies.
6. The success of the work will be adapted to larger scales in nuclear reactors and adopted for further improvements needed.

6. SUMMARY OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH

In our study, Platinum, Rhodium and Platinum Rhodium alloy were coated on SS304 by Electrodeposition method. In our work, around 1 micron thickness coating with around $0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of noble metal, was coated on steel. It reduced the overall cost of the raw materials. These coatings are used as catalyst for hydrogen generation, antibacterial studies, dye degradation and corrosion studies.

We have coated noble metals by DC and PC method with small amount by reducing cost effect to give more applications. These coatings are characterized by SEM, XRD and AFM. All these coatings were subjected for different applications. These coatings give similar results like pure noble metals.

In this research work, platinum group metals such as platinum, rhodium, and platinum-rhodium alloy coatings were generated by the electrodeposition method by adopting DC and PC techniques. The main intention of the work is to generate the coating in a short period of

time at a low temperature, without the additives, levellers, and organic agents in order to get bright, uniform, and uneven coatings. All the variables such as composition of the bath, pH, temperature, concentration, duration and current density were optimized in direct and pulse electrodeposition methods.

We prefer PC to DC for coating noble metals because DC electroplating consumes a large number of metal ions from the bath solution, resulting in poor coating. The PC plating process, on the other hand, would have been tremendously useful in terms of reducing the amount of noble metals consumed during plating, which might have had a range of industrial uses, as we studied in our research. Consequently, manufacturing costs will be reduced, production times will be reduced, and coating quality will improve. Furthermore, just one parameter, the current density, may be altered in traditional DC plating. The PC approach, on the other hand, offers three key features: peak current density, current ON time, and current OFF time can all be adjusted, and growth can be managed.

7. CHAPTER SCHEME

The thesis comprises seven chapters are as follows

Chapter 1 will give a general introduction to noble metals and properties of PGM's and an introduction to electrodeposition and its types. The basic concept of the different applications carried out in the research: dye degradation by photocatalytic method, its source; various dyes and their effects on the environment; introduction to hydrogen and its production; and antibacterial study using noble metals. Finally, this chapter explains the detailed literature survey and provides a brief summary of the work.

Chapter 2 describes the materials and experimental methods used throughout the study. It includes the introduction of substrate SS304 and its pre-treatment procedure, the experimental part of electrodeposition and bath optimization. It also presents the principles and instrument details of various characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction analysis, Scanning electron microscopy, Energy Dispersity X-ray spectroscopy, Atomic force microscopy and UV-Visible Spectrophotometer. This chapter also covers the principles involved in photocatalytic dye degradation, antibacterial research, and the hydrogen evolution reaction.

Chapter 3 describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings, applications in photocatalytic dye degradation mechanisms under UV irradiation and investigation of factors affecting the dye degradation process.

Chapter 4 this paper describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings and electrocatalytic performance of HER by linear sweep voltammetry, chronopotentiometry and Tafel measurements.

Chapter 5 covers the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum-rhodium alloy electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings, corrosion rate measurements by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, applications in photocatalytic dye degradation consisting of its mechanisms, and investigation of factors affecting the dye degradation process.

Chapter 6 paper describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings and electrocatalytic performance of HER by linear sweep voltammetry, chronopotentiometry, and Tafel measurements.

Chapter 7 Summarizes the results obtained in the present investigation and the scope for the future work.

8. SCOPE FOR THE FUTURE WORK

- Grain size, coating stability, throwing power, durability, and reduced thickness are some of the areas where future study could be focused.
- Hydrogen generation via the water splitting process may be scaled up to a low-cost synthesis technique for large quantities and photocatalytic dye degradation with various organic dyes can be examined.
- To combat bacterial growth, antibacterial investigations using additional noble metals, alloy and metal composites can be conducted.
- Innovative methods that have been tried and tested in the industrial business may be included in future study.
- Young researchers, scientists, and faculty members might also intend to use similar methodologies to acquire a better understanding of the progress and benefits of these proposed applications on a big scale industrial level.
- All this will assist in the simplification, economic development, and greening of the environment.

9. PAPERS PUBLISHED

1. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen (2019). A Review on Noble Metals in Controlling Intergranular Stress Corrosion Cracking in BWRs. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 3 (1): 53-59, ISSN No 2581-7000. <https://zenodo.org/record/2653464>
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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

MS	Mild steel
SS	Stainless steel
CA	Chronoamperometry
CV	Cyclic voltammetry
CP	Chronopotentiometry
PDP	Potentiodynamic polarization
EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
OCP	Open circuit potential
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction
EDX	Energy dispersive X-ray
AFM	Atomic force microscopy
JCPD	The joint committee on powder diffraction standards
FWHM	Full width half maximum
Ultraviolet	Ultraviolet visible spectroscopy
RhB	Rhodamine B
MB	Methylene blue
MO	Methyl orange

SYMBOLS

A	Ampere
Abs	absorbance
b_a	anodic Tafel slope
b_c	cathodic Tafel slope
cm	centimetre
C_{dl}	double layer capacitance
CR	Corrosion rate
E_{corr}	Corrosion potential
eV	electron volt
F	Faraday
g	gram
I	current
I_{corr}	Corrosion current
IE	Inhibition efficiency
ml	ml – milliliter
mV	millivolts
nm	nanometer

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CHAPTER – 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Noble metals

Precious metals are rare, naturally occurring metallic chemical elements with considerable economic worth. Precious metals are less chemically responsive than most different elements. They have a high lustre and are usually ductile. Precious metals were previously used as currency, however, they are now mostly employed as investment and commercial commodities. Gold, silver, platinum, and palladium are all given the ISO 4217 currency code. Gold and silver, the coinage metals, are the most well-known precious metals. Even though the fact that they both have industrial applications, they are most renowned for their applications in art, jewellery, and coinage. Other precious metals include ruthenium (Ru), rhodium (Rh), palladium (Pd), osmium (Os), iridium (Ir), and platinum (Pt), which belong to the platinum group metals (PGM's). The most widely traded metal is platinum [1]. Metals are in high demand as investments and as a measure of wealth, not just for their useful uses, but also in the automotive industry. According to chemistry, noble metals Ru, Rh, Pd, silver (Ag), Os, Ir, Pt, and gold (Au) are examples of noble metals) are metallic elements with exceptional chemical resistance, even at high temperatures [2]. Their catalytic properties and ability to speed up or slow down chemical reactions are well-known [3].

1.1.1 Platinum Group Metals (PGMs)

Metals other than Ag and Au, are collectively referred to as platinum group metals (PGM's). PGM elements make up transition metals in the d-block (groups 8, 9, and 10, periods 5 and 6). They are moreover divided into the iridium-group platinum-group elements (IPGEs: Os, Ir, Ru) and the palladium-group platinum-group elements (PPGEs: Rh, Pt, Pd). Based on how they behave in geological environments, noble metals are frequently employed in a variety of applications like the petroleum, chemical, electronic, electrical, marine industries and hence they are called "Industrial Vitamins". The abundance and distribution of naturally occurring noble metals in the earth's crust are both low. The majority of larger-scale platinum metal deposits are found at high altitudes. South Africa controls 90% of the world's platinum group metal resources, followed by Russia with 10%.

1.1.2 PGM physical and chemical qualities

PGMs have few distinct chemical and physical qualities. In general, they have a modest level of responsiveness. When it comes to reactivity, each metal's state of sub-division is critical. Pt and Pd are soluble in aqua regia (AR), but Rh, Ru, Ir, and Os are inert. PGM, on

the other hand, can be dissolved by strong alkaline oxidizing agents. Table 1.1 shows few of the PGM's effective chemical and physical qualities [4, 5].

Table 1.1 PGM's Chemical and physical qualities

	Ruthenium	Rhodium	Palladium	Osmium	Iridium	Platinum
Atomic Number	44	45	46	76	77	78
Density kgm ⁻³	12.2	12.4	12.0	22.5	22.4	21.45
Atomic Weight	101.07	102.91	106.42	190.2	192.22	195.08
Melting Point	2310	1986	1552	3045	2410	1772
Boiling Point	3900	3727	3140	5027	4130	3827
Oxidation States	+1,+2,+3,+4,+5,+6,+7,+8	+2,+3,+4,+6	+2,+4	+4,+4,+6,+8	+1,+2,+3,+4	+2,+4
First Ionization Potential (eV)	7.7	7.7	8.3	8.7	8.7	8.88
Hardness (Mho's Scale)	6.5	---	4.8	7.0	6-6.5	4.3

1.1.3 Major deposits and producing countries

The Bushveld igneous complex (South Africa), the NiCuPGM sulphide deposits of Nroil'sk in the Russian Arctic and placer deposits in the Ural mountains (Russia), Sudbury (Ontario, Canada), the Hartley mine (Zimbabwe), the Stillwater complex (Montana, USA), Northern Territory (Australia), and the Zechstein copper deposit in Poland are just a few of the major mines from which PGM is extracted. Naldrett [6] and Buchanan [7] books provide more useful information. As a result of the increased interest in PGMs and the better future potential, numerous additional deposits are being investigated. In addition, the search for new deposits is frequently prompted by uncertainty in the major supplying zones [8]. South Africa is the world's leading maker of PGMs, accounting for of global production 85% and 82% of global economic resources [9]. **Fig. 1.1** shows the major producers of platinum and rhodium.

Fig. 1.1 Major producers of Pt and Rh (in %) [10]

1.1.4 Areas of demand and application

The PGM's have numerous uses in a variety of areas as listed in the Fig. 1.2 Increased fashion knowledge has helped platinum, while gold remains the most popular metal for jewellery. Palladium is utilized as an alloying element and in jewellery as a whitening agent. Platinum, palladium, and rhodium are utilized in automobile catalysts to reduce carbon monoxide, unburned hydrocarbons, and nitrogen oxides in exhaust gases. On a base, an automobile catalytic converter contains 0.08 % Pt, 0.04% Pd, and 0.005-0.007% Rh [11]. Iridium is a newcomer to the field (Mitsubishi incorporated iridium-containing catalytic converters in its direct injection engines recently) [12]. As automobile exhaust emissions are strictly regulated, the need for PGM is increasing. While need in the developed world remains largely unchanged, the developing world's share is growing as more countries choose lower emission levels. PGM has a bright future in fuel cells, which is a significant industry segment [13]. A fuel cell is an electrochemical device that generates energy by combining hydrogen and oxygen.

Noble metals are good catalysts for certain chemical reactions and especially for hydrogen production in fuel cells. Usage of bulk metals is very costly and coating of thin layer of noble metal on steel is the best practice to achieve the desired goal. Different methods are available in literature to coat the thin layer of noble metal on steel surface. Electrodeposition method is more effective to achieve thin and adherent coating for these

applications. In electrodeposition, very small amount, like $0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ is coated to achieve the goal. These coated specimens are as good as pure noble metal.

Fig. 1.2 Demand of Pt and Rh (in %)[14].

1.2 Introduction to Electrodeposition

The discharge of metal ions present in the electrolyte at a cathodic surface initiates the electrodeposition of metallic layers from an aqueous solution. At the solid-electrolyte contact, the metal ion takes one or more electrons from the electrically conducting substance and then deposited them on the surface as metal atoms. External electrons are supplied through a DC source or a reducing agent in the solution surrenders the required electrons (electroless deposition). Anodic dissolution of sacrificial anodes made of the same metal as such which would be applied at the cathode, or the addition of metal salts to the solution, produce metal ions. Fig. 1.3 illustrates the process in a simplified form.

Fig. 1.3 Metal ions are transported from a sacrificial anode to the cathode, resulting in the formation of a metal deposit on the surface

Nowadays, Pulse electrodeposition is more promising than regular Direct Current Electrodeposition. In Pulse method, Current is given in different intervals by switch off and on method. It gives brighter and smaller nuclei compared to regular electrodeposition method.

1.2.1.1 Pulse Current (PC) Electrodeposition

Electroplating is the process of depositing a metallic coating on an electrode to create a surface with properties that differ from those of the base metal. Pulsed current electrodeposition is referred to as PC. Pulses can be used in conjunction with or overlaid on a DC feed. Due to the use of bipolar pulse, metal deposition occurs during the cathodic pulse period, with a small amount of metal getting redissolved during the anodic pulse period. The deposit's morphology and significant properties could be improved as a result of the frequent deposition and partial re-dissolution. Metal deposition by pulsed electrolysis is also known as pulse plating or pulsed-current plating

Interrupted direct current is used in pulse plating. It means that a series of direct current pulses with equal amplitude and duration are sent out. The pulses are synchronized and flow in the same direction. Between two consecutive pulses, there is a period of zero current. To meet the requirements of a given application, the pulse rate (frequency) and "ON" and "OFF" times (duty cycle) can be calculated. Fig. 1.4 depicts the pulsed current in its most basic form.

Fig. 1.4 Pulse current waveforms [15].

In pulse plating, the cathode layer is retained with numerous metal ions and is less impure. The metal ions near the cathode are depleted when the current is turned on, leaving a layer rich in water molecules. While the current is not flowing, metal ions from the plating solution diffuse into the layer next to the cathode. This procedure has been utilized numerous times. Gas bubbles and contaminants that have been absorbed on the cathode have a chance to desorb during the period the current is turned off. The average on time is between 0.1 and 9.9 milliseconds, and the average off time is between 1 and 99 milliseconds. When an ammeter is placed into a pulsed-current plating circuit, the average current is returned. The pulsed current patterns are shown in Fig 1.5 and Fig. 1.6 The average current must be the same with pulsed current as with continuous current in order to achieve the same plating rate. This can be accomplished by controlling the peak current, on-time, and off-time. By carefully selecting pulse-plating parameters, both the chemical and physical properties of the deposit can be precisely controlled.

➤ Is ideal pattern (b) Typical pattern as seen using an oscilloscope

Fig. 1.5 Current patterns in conventional pulsed-current plating

Fig. 1.6 Pattern of Pulsed Current

Pulse plating has the advantages of imparting the following properties to the coatings. corrosion resistance, aesthetic appearance, frictional characteristics, wear resistance, and hardness. Limiting current density boosts metal ion replacement in the dispersion layer even when the light is turned off. The thickness of the deposit is uniform due to improved adhesion. Physical and mechanical properties change as the rate of deposition increases. The use of adaptable pulse parameters help to alleviate the growth restriction. Lower porosity and less stress result from fine-grained deposits. Anodizing, as well as electroforming, electro cleaning, and etching, are all done with pulsed current. Pulse generators have the disadvantage of being more expensive than DC units. In order to achieve improved results, this method also necessitates proper planning in the form of a series of trials.

1.2.2 Advantages of pulse current for metal deposition

- ✓ Fine grained deposit
- ✓ Hard deposit
- ✓ Pore free deposit

- ✓ Improved metal distribution
- ✓ Improved tensile strength
- ✓ Low inclusion level
- ✓ High rate of deposition
- ✓ Improved physical properties
- ✓ Improved current efficiencies (in certain cases)
- ✓ Higher percentage of alloy content
- ✓ Low internal stress
- ✓ Reduced nodular growth
- ✓ Possibility of induced codeposition
- ✓ Improved properties of the composite

In our research work, we successfully carried out electrodeposition of selected noble metals that fall under the category of PPGEs (Rh, Pt, Pd). Namely, platinum and rhodium. The developed and optimized electrolytic bath for platinum, rhodium and platinum-rhodium alloy on SS304 was tested for different applications. The theory of these applications is discussed below.

1.3 Photocatalytic dye degradation

In the continuation of our applications-oriented research work, the third and major contribution is the photocatalytic dye degradation of methylene blue (MB). We are mainly interested in selecting this as one of our applications because water is a limited and valuable source, which is essential for well-being of human. Synthetic dyes are highly soluble in water, that are most well-known water pollutants observed in sewage from industry [16]. Synthetic dyes are widely used in several industries including paper, plastic, textile, cosmetics, food, concrete, etc. In industries, over than 10,000 different dyes and pigments are used [17]. In India, approximately 80% of the produced total dye-material is spent by the textile industry only. Several companies discharge wastewater with non-biodegradable residual dyes. Approximately 10 to 15% of the dye is lost in the sewage during the dyeing process. Contamination by dye wastewater is becoming more concerning as a result of the widespread usage of a wide range of colors. In the textile sector, 60-70% of dyes are utilized, and the majority of them are azo dyes and methylene blue dyes [18]. Several of these intermediates and reaction products are harmful and carcinogenic. As a result, the treatment of the effluent containing toxins is critical, as it can cause serious health concerns for humans, animals, and aquatic organisms. Textiles, paper, rubber, plastics, leather,

cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and food industries all utilise colours in large quantities nowadays, resulting in consistent market demand and production. There are currently over 10,000 synthetic dyes on the market, with over 7105 tonnes produced per year [19-20]. Synthetic dyes are made out of hydrocarbons obtained from coal tar, such as benzene, naphthalene, anthracene, toluene, xylene, and others, and have a complicated aromatic molecular structure [21]. Synthetic dye disposal is a major concern from an environmental standpoint [22]. Some of the most common dyes and their potential dangers are listed in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2 Some of the most common dyes and their potential dangers

Dye	Possibilities of Harm
Methylene Blue	Blood, reproductive system, liver, upper respiratory tract, skin and eye contact (irritant), and central nervous system are all toxic
Rhodamine B	In animals, it causes irritation of the respiratory tract, eye and skin irritation, digestive tract irritation, unfavorable reproductive and lethal consequences, vomiting, and diarrhoea.
Fast green	Tumors of the liver, testicles, or thyroid gland.
Fast ponceau diazo dye	It must never be touched during pregnancy because it is seriously toxic, sinful, and eye irritant.
Fast red salt B	Suspected carcinogen, eye and respiratory tract irritant, and extremely poisonous.
Malachite green	It builds up in the tissues, the liver, the thyroid gland, and the bladder.
Crystal violet	Mutagens and mitotic poison are both toxic to cells.
Eosin	Properties that are carcinogenic, estrogenic, and clastogenic.
Congo red	Mutagenic, dangerous if it comes into touch with the skin, and an eye irritant.
Diamond black	Mutagenic impact on thyroid cancer, DNA – damaging

We targeted MB degradation in our work and here is some brief notes on MB and its structure is shown in Fig. 1.7. In 1876, German chemist Heinrich Caro discovered methylene blue and it is produced using a procedure that was first familiarized in 1886 that uses dimethylaniline as the main raw substance. Methylene blue is a phenothiazine dye that is bright greenish blue in color. It is mostly used on bast (soft vegetable fibers like jute,

flax, and hemp), with some paper, leather, and mordant cotton thrown in for good measure. Silk and wool are dyed with it, but it has low lightfastness on these fibers. It's also employed as a chemical oxidation–reduction indicator and a biological stain for tuberculosis testing in milk.

Fig. 1.7 Structure of methylene blue

Purified water is not only essential for human consumption, but also for several different purposes. It is a crucial raw material for food processing, medical, pharmacological and chemical industries. There are different methods to treat wastewater [23]. Various methods employed in the treatment of wastewater are schematically provided in Fig .1.8.

Fig. 1.8 Conventional diagram of waste water treatment methods

Among these, photocatalysis is one of the techniques that can efficiently treat the waste. A combination of the words "photoreaction" and "catalysis" can be used to define the term "photocatalysis." It is a chemical change of a molecule generated by electromagnetic radiation absorption, or photoreaction, which is amplified by the presence of a catalyst. Photocatalysis emerges to be an exceptional strategy for water purification, with the feasibility of utilizing sunlight as a renewable and sustainable source of energy.

Photocatalysis is generally known as the activation of a chemical process by a solid photocatalyst irradiated by sunlight/UV-visible light source, it is well represented in the Fig. 1.9 [24]. Experimental parameters like the intensity of the radiation, humidity, reaction temperature, the amount of catalyst and availability of oxygen have significant effect on the rate of photocatalytic decomposition reactions [25].

Fig. 1.9 Schematic representation of photocatalysis reaction.

1.3.5 Significant Characteristics of a Photocatalyst

The best photocatalyst would possess the following significant characteristic features; It should be photoactive and able to utilize near UV light and visible light. Chemically and biologically inert, low cost, non-toxic and their redox potential must be negative. The metals such as Pt, Rh, Pd, Au, Ag and Si and metal oxide-based semiconductors like TiO_2 , ZnO, WO_3 , CdS, ZnS, $SrTiO_3$, SrO_2 , WS_2 , Fe_2O_3 , MoS_2 , BiOI, SiC, ect are widely used photocatalysts for dye degradation [26-28]. Among the metal catalysts, Pt, Ag and Si are the commercial heterogeneous photocatalysts. In these catalysts surface can be modified by adding impurity or decorated with semiconductor metal oxides and the surface-modified 6 metals can act as effective photocatalysts [29]. Example Pt coated metal-oxide catalysts are widely used as heterogeneous photocatalyst due to their large surface area with a porous surface and high stability.

1.4 Introduction to Hydrogen and its production

Another application was performed using our noble metal coated SS304 materials. This is used in the production of hydrogen. The Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) has already been examined in both acidic [30-32] and alkaline [33-34] solutions, as well as dependence towards pH and temperature effects. Several electrode materials had been used to

investigate HER, including Hg, Pt, Au, Sn, Cu and Ag [35-38]. Due to its high activity and zero overpotential, platinum is the best catalyst for HER [39]. Recently, alternatives to platinum catalysts have been the subject of a great deal of research. Catalysts based on molybdenum, nickel, cobalt, sulphides, selenides, and other chemicals have been investigated in this direction [40-44]. In an acidic media, these catalysts have excellent HER activity. However, in terms of overpotential and current densities, these catalysts do not compete with Pt. Furthermore, the production of these substances is both difficult and harmful to the environment.

Our main concerns towards evolution of hydrogen in small scale is, the extensive consumption of fossil fuels over the past century has led to serious concerns like global warming, ozone layer depletion and acid rain. A long term energy supply solution that is practical, low cost, and clean is required. Renewable energy sources like solar and wind can't be utilised as fuel directly, so they need to be stored. Among many choices, hydrogen has been identified as a potential energy source that can be stored, transported and distributed. Hydrogen is perhaps the most widespread element on the planet and is a leading option for use as an energy carrier. However, elemental hydrogen is not available in substantial quantity on earth and is found in combination with carbon in hydrocarbons and with oxygen in water. Hydrogen is not a source of energy, but only a carrier of energy and requires technology to be produced [45].

Hydrogen generated on-site using a variety of technologies could lead to development of decentralized micro power plants and vehicles based on hydrogen (fuel cells, internal combustion engine utilizing hydrogen) would dramatically reduce emissions of particulates, carbon monoxide, sulphur and nitrogen oxides and other local pollutants as the only by product of combustion is water [46].

Electrolysis, which involves splitting water into hydrogen and oxygen atoms using electricity, is a well-known method of obtaining hydrogen. Hydrogen can be produced electrochemically from water electrolysis utilising catalysts with long-term stability. It's critical to make large-scale, cost-effective practical applications possible. Currently, water electrolysis produces about 4% of the world's hydrogen (Committee on Hydrogen). Hydrogen can be created in a variety of ways, only a few of which are environmentally friendly. Hydrogen can be produced electrochemically from water electrolysis utilising catalysts with long-term stability, and it can be done with either aqueous alkaline electrolytes or solid polymer electrolytes. Water electrolysis necessitates the use of power, which can be obtained from clean and renewable sources. A crucial step toward a long-term

solution "Hydrogen energy resource" is the development of renewable, efficient, and cost-effective hydrogen production technologies [47]. A very clean hydrogen cycle would result from electrolysis using renewable energy. It also represents a potentially massive source of hydrogen, capable of meeting projected demand despite the fact that the price of providing electricity would initially be larger than that produced by fossil fuel/natural gas [48]. The cost is likely to decrease as technology and mass productions improve.

1.5 Antibacterial study

According to our current research, noble metals coated on SS304 samples which is in the form of circular discs are subjected to antibacterial study and their efficacy is monitored by the zone of inhibition. An antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of bacteria. Antimicrobial drugs are classified by the bacteria against which they are most effective. For at least 2000 years, antimicrobials have been widely used. To treat infections, the ancient Egyptians and Greeks used particular moulds and plant extracts. Microbiologists such as Louis Pasteur and Jules Francois Joubert discovered antagonism between bacteria in the nineteenth century and debated the benefits of managing these interactions in medicine [49].

Antimicrobial action is already used in a variety of situations, such as textile materials, water chlorination, pharmaceuticals, and packaged food [50]. Organic detergents, on the other hand, have some disadvantages, including toxicity to humans and antibiotic resistance [51]. According to noble metals were once thought to be useful in the treatment of diseases [52-55]. Because of metal nanoparticles, metal oxide, metal oxides doped with ions, metal ions, and metal salts' consistency, reliability, long life cycle, and safety, metal ions have gotten a lot of attention in recent decades. Noble metals have distinctive electronic and optical properties, making them promising antimicrobial channels [56]. As a result, current research focuses on noble metals such as Au, Ag, Pt, Pd, and Ru, as well as their alloys [57-58]. The noble metals which are named under PGMs (Ir, Os, Pd, Pt, Rh, and Ru) have comparable physical and chemical properties.

Using the agar petri plate and broth culture method, the antibacterial effect of platinum and rhodium was investigated against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive bacteria, in particular *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, *Bacillus Subtilis*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*. The name "Gram" comes from the Danish bacteriologist Hans Christian Gram, who developed the method "Grain" to distinguish the bacteria. The successful study was conducted against selected bacteria where our coated samples showed very good antibacterial agents by proving the electrodeposition of noble metals is one of the novelties

in this antibacterial study. The test is carried out by inoculating bacteria isolated from a patient's infection onto the surface of an agar plate. The plate is then incubated after coated samples in circular discs are put to the agar. If the bacteria are stopped from growing or killed by a coated sample, there will be a region around the disc where the bacteria have not grown large enough to be seen. This is referred to as "zone of inhibition" and showed in Fig. 1.10. Factors such as pathogen susceptibility, sample diffusion effects, agar depth, and size of the inoculated organism all make their contributions in the zone of inhibition [59].

Fig. 1.10 Petri plate showing before and after the antibacterial study.

1.6 Literature survey

1.6.1 Noble metal electrodeposition

1) M.E. Baumgartner (1988) developed the platinum and platinum alloys electrodeposition and this research has demonstrated that outstanding magnetic and mechanical properties may be deposited in platinum-cobalt alloys, and these alloy deposits appear to be very promising for data storage applications and thin permanent magnet layers [60].

2) S.S Djokic (2000) investigated electrodeposition of platinum from an alkaline electrolyte at 65⁰ C. The findings revealed that the current efficiency did not depend on the current density. Smooth, crack-free deposits were obtained when the thickness of the platinum layer was less than 5 μm [61].

3) S.D. Thompson et al. (2001) mentioned that their research focused on the electrochemistry of H₃Pt(SO₃)₂OH. In preliminary investigations, platinum was electro reduced from a solution of this complex acid onto glassy carbon (GC) and later onto

carbon-black (CB) based electrodes, similar to those employed in polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs). A sulphide or retained sulphite species is thought to have poisoned the electrodeposited platinum. In H_2SO_4 solution, platinum electrodes were electrochemically cycled between hydrogen and oxygen evolution potentials to activate the platinum and get a repeatable surface area [62].

4) R.Le. Penven et al. (1992) created the chemistry for a new commercial platinum electroplating bath based on a $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2^{2+}$ salt in a phosphate buffer. They used techniques such as ^{195}Pt NMR and microelectrodes. A homogeneous chemical reaction preceding the electron transfer phase is demonstrated to dictate the maximal rate of deposition; the nature of this homogeneous chemical reaction is described [63].

5) S.E. Hadian et al. (2000) demonstrated the processing conditions for the 'P' and 'Q' salt baths (containing platinum as diamminodinitrate) have been studied using electrochemical methods with a view to improving cathodic efficiency while maintaining an adequate current density [64]

6) C.R.K. Rao et al.(2006) demonstrated that platinum baths comprising $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_3(\text{NO}_2)](\text{NO}_2)$ and $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_2)$ have superior performance and electrodeposition behavior. The complex species ($\text{X}=\text{2CIP}$, 2NO_3^- and 2NO_2^-) in phosphate buffer onto titanium are characterized [65].

7) Steven Langerock et al. (2003) described the electrodeposition of rhodium on several polycrystalline gold substrates using $\text{Na}_3\text{RhCl}_6 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NaCl}$ solutions in his research paper. They used voltammetric and electrochemical quartz crystal microbalance techniques [66].

8) M. Sadeghi et al.(2004) used a thick electrodeposition of rhodium metal on a copper backing to target Rh preparation for the manufacture of ^{103}Pd . Electrodeposition studies were carried out in acidic sulphate media utilising $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ (recovered from hydrochloric acid solution), as well as commercially available Rhodex plating baths [67].

1.6.2 Photocatalytic dye degradation studies

1) T. Pauporte et al. (2007) used electrodeposited mesoporous ZnO thin films as efficient photocatalysts for the hydrothermal synthesis process to degrade dye pollution. The photocatalytic activity of zinc oxide films was evaluated using the photodegradation of a

hetero polyaromatic dye (methylene blue) and a diazo dye (congo red) as model reactions, with an efficiency of 86 % degradation. [68].

2) Milica Jovic et al. (2013) have reported that the electrochemical synthesis, structural, morphological, and optical characterization, as well as the photocatalytic activity of nanostructured ZnO films produced from zinc nitrate aqueous solutions. Up to 82 % of the methyl orange dye was destroyed [69].

3) Luminita Andronic et al. (2007) looked into the effect of the TiO₂ particular surface (powder, film) on methyl orange photocatalytic degradation (MO). Spray pyrolysis deposition was used to create a TiO₂ thin layer. According to this study, MO degraded by up to 87 % [70]

4) Li Fan et al. (2006) investigated the degradation of Amaranth azo dye in aqueous solution using an electrochemical technique under a potentiostatic condition using an activated carbon fibre (ACF) electrode. The largest amount of dye removed was 95.6 % [71].

5) Mohamed Gaber et al. (2013), with efficiencies of 97.9%, 96.65%, and 95.35%, author produced three modified electrodes (C/PbO₂, Pb + Sn/PbO₂ + SnO₂, and Pb/PbO₂) by electrodeposition and used them as anodes for electrochemical degradation of Reactive Yellow 160 (RY160) dye in aqueous solution [72].

6) Febgjun Zhang et al. (2014) found that in methyl orange degradation with high degradation percentages, that Pt/Pd co-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles had stronger photocatalytic activity than solo Pt/TiO₂ or Pd/TiO₂ nanoparticles [73].

7) Dayanne Chianca de Moura et al. (2015) investigated the electrochemical degradation of Acid Blue 113 dye using TiO₂-nanotubes coated with PbO₂ as anode. When Ti/TiO₂-Nanotubes/PbO₂ were tested with Rhodamine B, higher degradation efficiencies were observed [74].

8) Vanaja M et al. (2014) investigated stated that the green produced silver nanoparticles effectively degraded the MB dye by roughly 95%. after 4,320 minutes of UV exposure [75].

9) Jun Yao et al (2010) reported that absorption spectra of MB revealed that the maximum wavelength, 663 nm, was approximately the same. 92.3% of the pigment had been eliminated after 160 minutes [76].

9) A.C Nwanya et al. (2019) reported that the MB-dyed Zea mays L. dry husk mediated Bio-synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles had a 91% degrading efficiency [77].

1.6.3 Hydrogen generation studies

1) Mohammed A. Amin et al (2014) used cathodic polarization and employed silver nanoparticles mounted on titanium as active electrocatalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction using 0.1 M HCl solution. The findings demonstrate that the Ti substrate with the greatest population of AgNPs has the best electrocatalytic activity against the HER, even outperforming platinum. As a result, the Ti-AgNP catalysts as-prepared appear promising for catalysing the HER [78].

2) Manjeet Chhetri et al. (2017) compared the platinum electrode's electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction activity to that of the Ni/Ni(OH)₂/graphite electrode. Researchers have succeeded in manufacturing a low-cost Ni/Ni(OH)₂/graphite electrode with comparable performance to Pt. The proportional proportions of Ni and Ni(OH)₂ were appropriately chosen, resulting in a high current density with a low overpotential [79].

3) Xuan Liu Bo You et al (2017), according to author, competent and low-cost electrocatalysts are critical for the widespread use of electrocatalytic water splitting for clean H₂ production. They also discovered that following simple surface modification, commercially available stainless steel may be turned into competent electrocatalysts for both H₂ and O₂ evolution reactions (HER and OER, respectively) [80].

4) Yuchan Zhu et al. (2017) reported that developed high-efficiency electrochemical hydrogen evolution electrodes at a reasonable cost using the intermetallic Pt₂Si compound generated by magnetron sputtering. As observed in linear sweep voltammetry, the IM-Pt₂Si-MS electrode had a greater HER activity than a Pt electrode in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ solution (LSV). This is due to the electronic structural alteration of Pt and the synergistic effect of the Pt-Si binary alloy in the IM-Pt₂Si-MS electrode. They also discovered that following simple surface modification, commercially available stainless steel may be turned into competent electrocatalysts for both H₂ and O₂ evolution reactions (HER and OER, respectively) [81].

5) Lili Zhu et al. (2016) suggested the notion of rhodium/silicon co-electrocatalyst design to beat platinum hydrogen evolution activity at high overpotentials. This research reveals that the composite is more stable than rhodium nanoparticles and even outperforms commercial platinum/carbon composites at high over potentials [82].

6) Boguslaw Pirozynski et al. (2015) presented research on hydrogen cathodic development in Pt-modified nickel foam material. HER was investigated in a 0.1 M NaOH solution on platinum-activated nickel foam catalyst material grown spontaneously. When

compared to HER kinetics recorded on Pd/Ru-modified Ni foam catalyst materials, catalytic Pt modification of nickel foam resulted in a significant improvement [83].

1.6.4 Antibacterial studies

1) McQuitty (2014) investigated from many years ago, when studying metals, they were thought to be useful in the treatment of ailments. Because of the great efficiency of many metal-based treatments to overcome the drawbacks of metals on different diseases, such as bacteria and cancer, new advancements in contemporary medicine are recognized and confirmed in order to boost the activities of these metals [84].

2) Simon Paul Fricker (2007) according to a new study, the platinum anticancer medicine cisplatin has made a significant contribution to the treatment of testicular and ovarian cancer. This serendipitous discovery has sparked interest in other metal-based medicines. He also went over the several types of platinum medicines, from cisplatin to the third generation [85].

3) L. R Kelland (2000) investigated that, in medicine, platinum is used to make dental crowns and dental instruments, as well as anticancer drugs. Platinum has anticancer and antibacterial properties [86].

4) L. Oehninger et al. (2013) reported that the medical applications of rhodium include acting as anticancer and antibacterial drugs in the Rh(I), Rh(II), and Rh(III) forms [87].

5) Nishanthi et al. (2019) presented research on the green synthesis and characterization of bioinspired silver, gold, and PtNPs, as well as an evaluation of their synergistic antibacterial activity when coupled with a variety of antibiotic classes. The antibacterial activity of platinum metal particles was tested against human pathogenic bacteria before and after they were mixed with commercially available antibiotics and free drugs. Their discoveries open up new possibilities for treating antibiotic-resistant bacteria in a clinical context by combining several NPs, primarily noble metals [88].

6) Andrzej Wernicki et al. (2014) investigated antimicrobial properties of gold, silver, copper, and platinum nanoparticles were tested against selected bacteria isolated from cases of mastitis in cattle. In respect to the isolated microorganisms, the preparations' minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), and minimum fungicidal concentration (MFC) were measured [89].

7) Anju Arya et al. (2018) have been driven to manufacture biologically active nanoparticles due to the growth of infectious diseases and the rise in treatment resistance among bacteria, according to a recent publication. In the field of nanobiotechnology, environmentally acceptable processes for nanoparticle synthesis are evolving all the time.

In this study, we synthesized palladium and platinum nanoparticles from extract of the green alga *Botryococcusbraunii* and tested their antibacterial and antioxidant properties activity [90].

8) Misha Y. Vaidya et al. (2017) the effects of metal ions such as silver, copper, platinum, gold, and palladium on *Enterococcus faecium*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were examined separately and in combination. In zone of inhibition (ZOI) testing, platinum, gold, and palladium demonstrated the highest antibacterial efficiency. When these metals were tested together, they exhibited signs of synergy [91].

9) Zdenek Kolarik (2003), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was used to assess the bacterial adherence and bactericidal properties of the Ag and Ag/Pt coated polymers, while fibroblast cells were used to test the cytotoxicity. The antibacterial efficiency of the Ag coatings was greatly improved by adding 1% Pt [92].

1.7 Brief Summary

In our study, Platinum, Rhodium and Platinum Rhodium alloy were coated on SS304 by Electrodeposition method. In our work, around 1 micron thickness coating with around 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of noble metal, was coated on steel. It reduced the overall cost of the raw materials. These coatings are used as catalyst for hydrogen generation, antibacterial studies, dye degradation and corrosion studies.

We have coated noble metals by DC and PC method with small amount by reducing cost effect to give more applications. These coatings are characterised by SEM, XRD and AFM. All these coatings were subjected for different applications. These coatings give similar results like pure noble metals.

In this research work, platinum group metals such as platinum, rhodium, and platinum-rhodium alloy coatings were generated by the electrodeposition method by adopting DC and PC techniques. The main intention of the work is to generate the coating in a short period of time at a low temperature, without the additives, levellers, and organic agents in order to get bright, uniform, and uneven coatings. All the variables such as composition of the bath, pH, temperature, concentration, duration and current density were optimised in direct and pulse electrodeposition methods.

We prefer PC to DC for coating noble metals because DC electroplating consumes a large number of metal ions from the bath solution, resulting in poor coating. The PC plating process, on the other hand, would have been tremendously useful in terms of reducing the

amount of noble metals consumed during plating, which might have had a range of industrial uses, as we studied in our research. Consequently, manufacturing costs will be reduced, production times will be reduced, and coating quality will improve. Furthermore, just one parameter, the current density, may be altered in traditional DC plating. The PC approach, on the other hand, offers three key features: peak current density, current ON time, and current OFF time can all be adjusted, and growth can be managed.

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CHAPTER-2

METHODS AND MATERIALS

2.1 Introduction

Direct Current electrodeposition (DC) and Pulse Current electrodeposition (PC) techniques were used to coat SS304 with platinum, rhodium, and platinum-rhodium alloy. The process involves choosing an appropriate electrolytic solution that containing complex ions of platinum and rhodium, then fine-tuning the composition to ensure homogeneous metal ion dispersion in the electrolyte. Manual, mechanical, and chemical approaches were used to prepare the electrode surface. Variation of experimental parameters such as temperatures, pH, bath concentration and operation parameters were used to electrodeposit noble metals using DC and PC methods. The deposits were characterized using FESEM, EDX, XRD and AFM, they were evaluated for their applications in the fields of corrosion resistance on SS304, MB dye degradation, hydrogen evolution and microbial mitigation.

2.2 Preparation of stainless steel sample

Stainless steel 304 (SS304) Fig. 2.1 and its chemical composition Table 2.1, samples of 1 mm thickness were cut with the help of a laser machine to get circular discs of 15 mm diameter. A 2 mm hole is drilled at a distance of 2 mm from the edge of the disc. With an overall 1.76 cm² surface area facing one side of the disc. To produce a smooth finish, polished SS304 surfaces were rubbed with 600 to 2500 grade emery paper, then polished with alumina powder (1.0, 0.3, and 0.05 mm grades) using a wet polishing cloth. Then they were degreased by washing with acetone. Finally they were washed with deionised water, Fig. 2.2 shows polished SS304 samples. A DC source of N6705B, from Keysight Technologies, was used as a current source. The electrodeposited coatings were washed with distilled water and air-dried. They were kept in desiccators until further use.

Table 2.1 Chemical composition of SS304 specimen

Elements	C	Mn	P	Cr	Ni	Si	S	Fe
SS304	0.08	2.00	0.045	18.0-20.0	8.0-12.0	0.75	0.030	Balance

Fig. 2.1 SS304 without polish coupon **Fig. 2.2** SS304 with polish coupon

2.3 Experimental Set Up

Platinum tetrammonium hydrogen phosphate $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{HPO}_4$ and rhodium sulphate $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ salts were procured from Arora Matthey Limited, Kolkata, India as platinum and rhodium sources respectively. The platinum 5Q bath is based on the phosphate buffer complex and rhodium in the form of sulphate ions. Noble metals were deposited on the SS304 specimen by DC and PC methods using platinum, rhodium and a combination of the two in a bath solution containing a different concentration of metal ions to maintain suitable operating parameters. Fig. 2.3 Constituents of the bath solution are prepared from different concentrations of platinum tetrammonium hydrogen phosphate, rhodium sulphate and H_2SO_4 . As mentioned in table 2.3.3, platinum bath does not consist of H_2SO_4 , whereas the rhodium and platinum-rhodium baths do. The bath solution was adjusted with the respective pH values (acidic for rhodium and alloy coatings and basic for platinum coatings) prior to the electrodeposition. In the electrodeposition process, the anode was platinized titanium, which acts as durable metal strip. The cathode is SS304, and the coated sample is shown in (Fig. 2.4 for platinum and Figure 2.5 for platinum-rhodium alloy). The temperature was slowly increased and the optimum value was noted. To achieve the deserved coatings based on various modes of application proposed in our research work, the electrolytic bath was maintained with optimized pH, temperature, and current density.

Fig 2.3 Representation of electrodeposition of alloy on SS304

Fig. 2.4 Platinum coated on SS304

Fig. 2.5 Platinum-Rhodium coated on SS304

2.3.1 Electrodes

In electrochemical analysis of corrosion inhibition, three electrode configuration was used. The three electrodes are

- 1) Working.
- 2) Counter.
- 3) Reference.

In the present study, Ag/ AgCl electrode was used as the reference electrode and platinum electrode or platinized titanium used as counter electrodes.

2.3.2 Electrolytic Bath

Three electrolytic baths were optimized in our research, as shown in tables 2.2, 2.3 and 2.4. These baths are adaptable, simple to use, low-cost, repeatable, and ideal for technological applications such as dye degradation, hydrogen evolution and anti-bacterial research. To

achieve good deposits with improved material qualities, the prepared bath must be free of metallic, organic, and insoluble contaminants. The entry of any contaminant can be prevented by thoroughly cleaning the electrodes before use. The working conditions have an impact quality of coatings. For applications, it is critical to get good deposits with outstanding material properties with this fact in the bath has been optimized for all operating parameters.

Table 2.2 Optimized electrolytic bath composition and other deposition controlling parameters for platinum coating.

Components	Parameters
Platinum Solution [Pt (NH ₃) ₂] HPO ₄	0.2 g/l
Temperature	50°C
pH	10.5
Current density	2.5 A/dm ²
Deposition time	12 min
Duty cycle	DC method and 25%,50%75%

Table 2.3 Electrolytic bath and deposition controlling parameters for rhodium coating.

Composition	Parameters
Rh ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.0075 g/l
H ₂ SO ₄	5 ml
Temperature	40°C
pH	1.5
Current density	4.5 A/dm ²
Deposition time	18 min
	PC: 25%, 50% and 75%
Coating Source	DC

Table 2.4 Electrolytic bath and deposition controlling parameters for platinum-rhodium alloy coating.

Components	Parameters
Platinum solution [Pt (NH ₃) ₂] HPO ₄	1.5 ml
Rhodium sulphate solution Rh ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.075 ml
H ₂ SO ₄	5 ml
Electrodeposition parameter	
Heat	40 °C
pH	1.2
Current density	4.0 A/dm ²
Installation time	18 min
PC Duty cycle	25%, 50 % and 75%
DC	Direct current flow

2.4 Electrolytic bath parameters

2.4.1 Current density

To determine effect of current density on coating, it was adjusted from 1.0 A/dm² to 10.0 A/dm². The coating produced at the lower current density are brilliant, uniform, and regular. Coating at a very low current density, below 2.0 A/dm², results in brittle coating and lower covering power. A burnt deposit is produced when the current density exceeds 5.0 A/dm². In electrodeposition, current density is a critical parameter for achieving the required coating. When compared to other current densities, optimum current density provides good throwing and covering power. Optimum current density has mentioned in the above table.

2.4.2 Duty cycle

Deposition was performed at 25, 50, and 75% duty cycles in both the PC and DC methods. When compared to the PC approach, the coating morphology in the DC method was not homogeneous and had larger grain sizes. Coating obtained at 75% in the PC technique is more consistent, with a smaller grain size, as compared to coating obtained at 25% and 50%. Fresh nuclei are produced in the PC technique, which results in homogeneous and decreased grain coatings during the ON and OFF times of the current. The grain sizes were almost the same in 25% to 50% duty cycle cases as in the DC approach. Nuclei are generated in the DC technique, and the expansion of the same nuclei results in larger grain sizes. When compared to other processes, the PC approach at a 75% duty cycle produces a brilliant, uniform, and small-grained coating in our preparations [1].

2.4.3 pH

The pH and temperature of the bath must be kept within a specific range to achieve appropriate coating [2]. The pH of the bath in each experiment was measured using a calibrated pH metre, and the results were recorded. Microprocessor-based pH metre (HANNA-Singapore, Model no. pH 211; accuracy 0.01 pH, range 1.00 to 14.00 pH, and temperature -9.9°C to 120°C was utilised in this study (Fig. 2.6).

Fig. 2.6 pH meter

2.4.4 Temperature:

In our investigations, we employed a Microprocessor-based Magnetic Stirrer with Hot Plate and External Temperature Sensor (DRAGON LABS – China, model no. MS7-H550-Pro; having digital speed control, programmable and automatic temperature management) to maintain the temperature conditions, shown in (fig. 2.7) . Normally, hydrogen evolution on the cathode results in burnt deposits at extremely low pH values, whereas at higher pH levels, the electrode surface becomes coated with insoluble hydroxides. Similarly, at lower temperatures, electrodeposition rates were reduced, while at higher temperatures, weak deposits and occasionally burnt deposits were formed due to the generation of H₂ gas [3]. As a result, a number of studies were conducted for DC and PC methods to optimize pH and temperature. Studies were carried out using baths at pH 2-6 and pH 10-11 and temperatures ranging from 30° to 50°C. For maintain basic and acidic pH conditions, respectively, NaOH and HCl were used. At 50⁰ C, the electrolyte undergoes more dissociation, resulting in the maximum metal ion concentration in the bath solution and a uniform coating. Fresh nucleic generated at a higher rate than nuclei development at this temperature, resulting in a homogeneous and reduced grain size coating. Burnt and uneven deposits were detected at 60⁰C and above. As a result, we've settled on 50⁰ C as the ideal temperature for our research.

Fig. 2.7 Temperature set up in the lab.

2.5 Platinized titanium anode

Fig. 2.8 a shows the photograph of typical platinized titanium meshes. A titanium anode that has been platinized is simply one that has been coated with platinum or platinum metal oxides. Platinized titanium anodes are non-consumable and long-lasting inert anodes. Under the lab conditions, these anodes are insoluble in the electrolyte [4]. The fabrication & supply of platinum plated mesh for electroplating was from Ti anode fabricators Pvt. Ltd. Madampakkam, Chennai, India.

The following are some of the benefits of platinized titanium anodes

- Plating times were shortened
- Secondary operations, such as grinding, are reduced or eliminated.
- The geometry of the anode essentially stays the same throughout time, providing for reliable plating results (Fig. 2.9)
- Long-term performance
- Maintenance-free
- Longer bathing life
- Lightweight and energy efficient

These anodes are employed in a number of applications.

- Treatment facilities for sewage
- Chlorate and perchlorate generation through electrosynthesis
- Electro-chlorination
- Cathodic protection and electroplating

Fig. 2.8. Platinized titanium mesh used as anode

Fig. 2.9. Platinized titanium anode mesh after several cycles of electroplating showing long operative life.

2.6 Instruments and apparatus

Using a current source, N6705B Keysight technologies, modular, 600 W, 4 Slot, Santa Rosa, USA (Fig. 2.10), DC and PC electrodeposition were carried out. The electrochemical analyzer model CHI608D, Austin, USA, with a three-electrode cell assembly, was used to perform linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), chronoamperometry (CA), chronopotentiometry (CP), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). Scanning electron microscopy was performed using FESEM Carl Zeiss equipment. The energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) investigation was performed using a Model: Oxford Instrument 250 scanning electron microscope. The Rigaku miniflex II desktop X-ray diffractometer (1.54 Å, CuK_α radiation) was used for the X-ray diffraction studies. Studies on AFM were done by Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM & STM. Agilent technology Cary-60 eclipse spectrophotometer instrument was used for photocatalytic dye degradation studies.

Fig. 2.11 Keysight technologies model N6705B instrument

2.7 Electrochemical techniques

2.7.1 Corrosion measurements

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a powerful method to study the corrosion of coated metallic samples. CHI608E (electrochemical workstation), Austin, USA instrument (Fig. 2.12) with a conventional three-electrode cell consisting of Ag/AgCl as reference electrode, platinum as counter electrode and a blank/coated SS304 disc as a working electrode with 1.76 cm² exposed area [5]. EIS is an efficient method to study the corrosion performance of the coated metallic samples. EIS measurements were done by enforcing a small sinusoidal AC potential perturbation of 10 mV between the frequency range of 0.01 Hz – 0.1 MHz to the metal at constant open circuit potential (OCP) in 0.1M Na₂SO₄ solution.

Fig. 2.12 Electrochemical analyzer instrument CHI608D

2.7.2 Linear sweep voltammetry

LSV is a method where the current at working electrode is measured with the linear sweep of electrode potential with time as shown in Fig. 2.13 (A). Figure 2.14 (B) shows the measurement of the working electrode current with respect to potential applied. In LSV, only the first half cycle of a cyclic voltammogram is executed. LSV is used to identify the unknown species and to determine the concentration of the solution. $E_{1/2}$ is used for identifying unknown species and the limiting current is used to determine the concentration. LSV is used to compare the performance of catalysts for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) as well.

Fig. 2.13 (A) Potential time functions for the excitation signal in linear sweep voltammetry and Fig. 2.14 (B) typical linear sweep voltammogram for electrochemical reaction [6].

2.7.3 Chronoamperometry

Chronoamperometry is a technique for measuring the electric current in an electrolytic cell over time at a constant applied voltage. A stationary working electrode and undisturbed fluid are typically employed in this experiment. The current-time curve depicts the change in the concentration gradient in the vicinity of the electrode surface under these conditions, and mass transfer is purely by diffusion. As time passes, the diffusion layer gradually expands due to the depletion of analyte species, resulting in a decreasing slope of the concentration profile [7]. Accordingly, the current decays with time, as given by the Cottrell equation indicated below:

$$I_p(t) = nFACD^{1/2}\pi^{-1/2}t^{-1/2}$$

where n , F , A , C , D and t are the number of electrons, Faraday's constant, the surface area of electrode, the concentration of the analyte, the diffusion coefficient and time, respectively.

This method is frequently used to determine the diffusion coefficient of electroactive species and the working electrode's surface area. Furthermore, several analytical applications of this method rely on pulsing of the working electrode's voltage at predetermined time intervals. This technique is being utilized to examine the stability of electrocatalysts and photo-electrocatalysts, as well as to determine a wide range of bioactive chemicals at bare and modified electrodes. The double layer potential step method is used to measure the rate constant of chemical reaction and the adsorption process. Chronoamperometry measurements under the hydrodynamic condition enhance the mass transport of electroactive species and hence the sensitivity of the detection is enhanced.

2.7.4 Chronopotentiometry

Chronopotentiometry is a frequently used technique that involves applying current to an electrode and measuring the potential changes over time. When the flux of redox species to the surface reaches a point where it can no longer support this current, the potential shifts swiftly to a new value at which another species is reduced or oxidized. This time span is known as transition time τ , and it is determined by the Sand equation [8]

$$\tau^{1/2} = \pi^{1/2} n F D^{1/2} C^* / 2i_0$$

Where i_0 is the current density (i/A). Diffusion coefficients can be calculated using the above equation. The advantage of chronopotentiometry is that the τ value is directly proportional to D , and that τ is the same regardless of heterogeneous electrode kinetics.

2.8 Spectroscopic analysis/characterization

Characterization of coatings for corrosion, photocatalytic dye degradation, hydrogen liberation, and antibacterial study was carried out using spectroscopic techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD) spectroscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) equipped with an attachment for Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS or EDAX) analysis, and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) (AFM).

2.8.1 XRD analysis

It is a non-destructive method for characterizing crystalline materials. It is a common useful method for determination of the percentage of crystallinity, size, strain, lattice parameters and crystalline phases, with subsequent quantitative phase identification. The deposits were examined using a Rigaku Miniflex 600 XRD (Fig. 2.15). An analysis was undertaken to investigate coating properties such as preferred orientation of crystallites and to compute the average crystallite size of deposit obtained by DC and PC methods.

Fig. 2.15 RigakuMiniFlex 600 XRD instrument

The electrodeposits of DC and PC with a surface area of 1.76 cm^2 were positioned on the aluminium holder and placed into the instrument's analysing chamber using mounting tweezers. All of the samples were incident with CuK_α radiation at a wavelength of 1.54 \AA and inspected for 90 minutes at 40kV and 15mA at a scan rate of 1° per minute. The peaks in the diffractogram were assigned hkl indices indexed using JCPDS Card numbers. The resulting X-ray diffraction patterns resembled fingerprints of the crystals in the sample.

2.8.2 SEM and EDAX analysis

Carl Zeiss, USA was used to acquire and analyse SEM images in order to evaluate deposit surface morphology. SEMs are typically equipped with an attachment for Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS or EDAX) (Model: Oxford EDS) (Fig. 2.16). SEM analysis is a technique used to identify chemical, textural, orientation, and structural information in a variety of specimens with length scales ranging from micrometers to nanometers. SEM uses a focused electron probe (with high energy electrons) to generate multiple signals in a region of interest on the sample point-by-point to capture a two-dimensional image of the surface to characterize a wide range of specimens. EDAX analysis reveals the presence of different elements and composition, and the particle compositions on the surface of coatings. The EDAX detector converts X-rays emitted by various atoms or ions on the specimen's surface into an energy spectrum, resulting in energy peaks corresponding to the presence of certain atoms or particles.

The electrodeposits of DC and PC with a surface area of 1.76 cm² were mounted on the adhesive lifts of the specimen holder with mounting tweezers and introduced into the instrument's analysing chamber. The electron beams were incident on a 1.76 cm² zone of electrodeposits with an acceleratory potential stroked energy of 5kV-15kV. Images of the electrodeposits were taken at magnifications ranging from 500X to 10000X. Following the SEM examination, the same samples were subjected to EDAX analysis with the appropriate settings to determine the composition of the electrodeposits. Electron beam penetrates upto a depth of 1 to 2 microns by accelerating voltages ranging from 10kV to 20kV.

Fig. 2.16 Carl Zeiss, Germany with oxford model EDS, SEM equipped with EDS instrument

2.8.3 AFM analysis

AFM pictures were taken and analysed using an Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM & STM Atomic Force Microscope, similar to SEM studies, to characterise the surface morphology of deposits (Fig. 2.17). AFM analysis is a technique for characterising a wide range of specimens from micrometre to nano meter length scales in order to get information of surface physical attributes such as local sample height, particle granular size, surface temperature, surface potential, friction, hardness, and so on.

The electrodeposits of DC and PC with a surface area of 1.76 cm² were mounted on the adhesive lifts of the specimen holder with mounting tweezers and introduced into the instrument's analysing chamber. The laser beams were incident on the 1.76 cm² region of electrodeposits. All electrodeposits were photographed at 5m x 5m, 10m 10m, 20m 20 m, and 40m 40m resolutions, with heights ranging from 10nm to 400nm.

Fig. 2.17 Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM & STM Atomic force microscope

2.9 Photocatalytic degradation

The photocatalytic degradation experiment was performed using Methylene Blue (MB) as a dye under ambient atmosphere conditions. Photocatalytic experiments were carried out at the centre of the cylindrical photoreactor (Fig. 2.18), which consists of a light source (here, a UV light lamp, 300 W, absorbance at 664 nm (UV–Vis absorption spectra)) surrounded by eight quartz reactor tubes (each 100 mL in volume), 37 cm in height and 2.3 cm in inner diameter, as well as cooling fans (Fig. 2.19). A reaction mixture consisting of a catalytic load of different electrodeposited platinum, rhodium and platinum-rhodium alloy coated samples with two different current sources, namely DC and PC, with 25%, 50% and 75%, respectively. The suspension was stirred in the dark for 3 hours. The solution was irradiated under UV light at a constant temperature. Samples were also collected every 30 minutes to evaluate the percentage of MB degradation.

A visible annular photoreactor (Agilent technology Cary-60) was purchased from the scientific company "HEBER" in Chennai, India for use in photocatalytic studies (Figure 2.20). Initially, the photocatalytic dye degradation of all coated samples was studied. The samples with the maximum MB dye degradation were determined, and the experiment was repeated to test the sample efficiency with additional factors such as dye concentration, stability, different scavengers, and pH range.

The percentage of photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes has been determined as follows.

$$\% \text{ of degradation} = [(C_a - C_b) / C_a] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{equation -1}$$

Where C_a and C_b is initial and final dye concentration respectively.

Fig. 2.20 Agilent technology Cary-60 - UV-visible spectrophotometer

Fig. 2.18 Photograph of HEBER multilamp cylindrical photoreactor

Fig. 2.19 Inside of multilamp cylindrical photoreactor surrounded by eight quartz reactor tubes.

2.10 Antibacterial test

The test was carried out against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria [28]. Furthermore, utilising a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM), the deformed cell wall of bacteria after reacting with antibacterial drugs was validated (AFM). The cytotoxicity of antibacterial drugs was investigated using the MTT test.

2.10.1 Sample preparation for antibacterial assay

The coated samples were put into wells of Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates using dissecting forceps (Fig. 2.21).

Fig. 2.21 Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA) plates.

2.10.2 Bacterial strains used for test

The Gram positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacterial strains were used in this study. Gram-negative *E. coli* and Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, *Bacillus Stilis* and *Enterococcus faecalis* were cultured on Mueller Hinton Broth. All four bacteria used for platinum and rhodium coated antibacterial studies were obtained from the Saphthagiri Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre (SIMSRC) in Bengaluru, Karnataka, South India. The strains were placed on nutrient agar gradients which were maintained at 4°C. Every time before conducting a new experiment fresh cells were revived on MHA plates.

2.10.3 Preparation of inoculum

All four bacteria were used to make inoculums, which were made from a 24 hour old culture. The tips of five colonies were transferred to a tube containing 5 mL Mueller Hinton broth using sterile loops. The tubes were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The turbidity of the culture suspension was controlled with a 0.9 percent saline solution. The culture density was set to 0.5 McFarland standards. For preparing medium, the materials required are: Peptone 5 g, yeast extract 2 g, sodium chloride 5 g, agar 15 g, and 1000 mL Double distilled water.

2.10.4 Agar well diffusion method

The antibacterial activity of antimicrobial drugs was tested using the well diffusion method [9-10] against various bacterial strains for the samples obtained from both PC and DC method. The surface of agar plates was infected for this test by spreading a volume of microbial inoculum across the entire plate. A sterile cork tip was used to pierce a hole with a diameter of 5 mm, and 50 mL of each antimicrobial agent was poured into the well. Finally,

the agar plates were incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours. The testing agent spreads throughout the agar medium, inhibiting the development of both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria strains. The inhibitory zone was found on the plates after the incubation phase (Fig. 2.22).

Fig. 2.22 Agar plate with zone of inhibition in the centre for Pt-Rh coated sample.

2.11 Hydrogen evolution reaction

The electrochemical cell was designed for quantitative measurement of hydrogen (Fig. 2.23), where the electrodeposited prepared noble metal platinum, rhodium and platinum-rhodium alloy electrode were subjected to cathodic polarization, respectively. Electrodeposited coatings obtained under different deposition conditions were used as the test electrode and platinum electrode with a high surface area was used as the counter electrode. A saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as the reference electrode. All potentials reported in the present study are concerning SCE and converted to a standard hydrogen electrode (SHE).

Electrochemical behaviour of the coatings, in terms of HER, was evaluated by subjecting it to cyclic voltammetry, linear sweep voltammetry and chronopotentiometry studies in 0.5M H₂SO₄ medium, using computer-controlled using an electrochemical workstation (compactstat.h 10800 from Ivium Technologies, Netherlands) (Fig. 2.24). The cell was fitted with a graduated gas collector where the liberated hydrogen replaces the corresponding

amount of solution. This facility allows relating the amount of gas liberated at a given time for electrode materials deposited at a given current density.

Fig. 2.23 Electrochemical cell designed for HER **Fig. 2.24** An electrochemical workstation compactostat.h 10800 is connected to computer

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CHAPTER – 3

**Application in photocatalytic
dye degradation:
Platinum electrodeposition**

3.1 Introduction

More than 150 years earlier, Elkington, who received a patent in 1837 [1] and later Bijtger, developed the first experiments on the electrolytic deposition of platinum group metals [2]. There has been a substantial increase in the supply of chemical and electrochemical deposition methods for platinum metals, especially for platinum as illustrated by recent literature [3-5]. In solar panels, fuel cells, boiler reactors etc., platinum group metals are used more advantageously as strong catalysts. Because of their relative inertness, ability to catalyze complex chemical reactions, and biocompatibility, noble metals are extensively utilized in commercial applications. It's also non-toxic and non-explosive, which is an added plus. Low tension, brilliant, adhesive, and uniform deposition is required for this system [6-8]. Due to their high cost, bulk metals are frequently replaced with a thin layer of metal deposited on less expensive electrode supports [9]. These applications require a different type of morphology and structure. Production of such coating for various applications with nano and micro size is a great challenge [10-11].

The electrodeposition method is considered a simple, efficient, effective and economical method to produce a noble metal coating. It is obtained in a simple metal salt solution for a small duration. Platinum is a very expensive metal and the electrodeposition method gives very thin and adherent coating in small duration for various applications [12-14]. In this method, by varying the bath parameters we can achieve the different grain sizes from nano-size to micro size, thickness, porosity and adhesion properties [15-17]. Nowadays PC method is more attractive and beneficial because it produces uniform, adherent and more refined coating than the DC method

The electrochemical method for dye pollution treatment has recently received a lot of attention, owing to its ease of automation, high sustainability, and environmental friendliness [18-20]. The traditional methods were inadequate to purify the wastewater, simply moving the compounds from aqueous to another phase, causing secondary pollutants [21-22]. Photocatalysis in presence of noble metals like platinum is considered the best method for effluent treatment. Effluents can be converted into potable water with platinum as a catalyst is a simple and effective method.

Green manufactured silver nanoparticles were utilized to effectively degrade the MB dye by about 95% after 4,320 minutes of exposure time [23]. Efficiency of MB dye degradation was 96% in electrodeposited platinum-rhodium on SS304 [24]. The absorption spectra of MB revealed that the highest wavelength, 663 nm, was nearly the same, according to Jun Yao et

al. After 160 minutes, 92.3% of the pigment had been removed [25]. Environmental remediation of MB dye in water by synthetic sodium silicate magadiite nanosheets [26]. Catalytic metal and combined oxides of Cu, Zn and Al are widely utilized in engineering chemical production and pollution management [27-28]. The presence of catalytically active transition metal species (e.g., Cu, Co, Fe, Ni, V, 26Rh, Ph), the final products easily undergoes separation [29-30].

In this work, Platinum metal was coated on SS304 by simple DC and PC method. All the coatings were characterized and platinum coated samples were evaluated for the dye degradation process.

3.2 Materials and method

Platinum 5Q plating solution from Arora Matthey Limited, Kolkata, had been used. The Q bath is based on the phosphate buffer complex $[Pt (NH_3)_4] HPO_4$ at pH 10.5. The electroplating bath was prepared by taking 0.15 ml from 5Q solution and makeup to the mark by using distilled water to 50ml. 10% NaOH has been added to adjust the solution pH. SS304 samples were mechanically polished using different grade emery paper ranging from 100 to 2500 before electrodeposition. Platinized titanium metal was taken as anode and SS304 with 15 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness with 1.76 cm^2 surface area was used as a cathode to coat platinum [31-32]. A beaker cell containing 50 cm^3 of electrolytic bath solution was used for coating. DC Source of N6705B from Keysight Technologies was used as a current source. The electrodeposited coatings obtained were washed with distilled water and air-dried. Optimized bath composition is listed in Table 3.1.

SEM was performed for microstructural characterization of the coatings and EDX was used to determine their composition. Atomic force microscope (AFM, (Nanosurf® EasyScan AFM& STM)) analyzed the average roughness of the coatings.

Photodegradation studies on MB by electrodeposited platinum coated on SS304 material were assessed under UV light irradiation. In a quartz photo reactor holding 100 mL of 5 mg/L MB, platinum coated samples were used as photocatalysts. For 3 hours, the suspension was agitated in the dark. At a steady temperature, the solution was radiated under UV light. The absorbance at 664 nm (UV-Vis absorption spectra) was used to assess the residual MB (aqueous solution). Every thirty minutes, samples were taken to measure the percentage of MB degradation. For organic dyes, the proportion of photocatalytic degradation was computed as.

$$\% \text{ of degradation} = [(C_0 - C_t) / C_0] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where C_0 is the initial absorbance of the MB dye solution,
 C_t is the absorbance of the MB dye solution at certain time intervals of degradation.

3.3 Results and Discussions

3.3.1 Bath Parameters optimization

3.3.1.1 Effect of pH

In platinum coating, a good coating will be obtained in between pH 10 to 10.6. Even though there may be not many changes observed in the coating morphology outside this pH range. If we maintain the pH of 10 to 10.5, the current efficiency of the coating was good [33]. In our studies also below 10 and above 11 give a dull and uneven coating. It was also not covered in the entire region of the metal. We have achieved a bright coating at 10.5. In this study, pH was fixed at 10.5 for further studies.

3.3.1.2 Current Density

The current density was varied from 1.0 A/dm^2 to 5.0 A/dm^2 to know the effect on its coating. The coating obtained at 2.5 A/dm^2 gives the bright, uniform and regular coating. 2.0 A/dm^2 gives brittle coating and covering power was less. Current density above 3.0 A/dm^2 gives burnt deposit. Current density is a very important parameter to achieve the desired coating in electrodeposition. At 2.5 A/dm^2 gives good throwing power and covering power compared to other current densities.

3.3.1.3 Temperature

The coating was done at room temperature up to 90° C . Coating at 50° C gives the bright coating compare to other temperatures. The coating obtained below 50° C gives a frosted appearance with uneven coating [34]. At 50° C electrolyte undergoes more dissociation and gives the highest metal ion concentration in the bath solution by giving the uniform coating. At this temperature, fresh nuclei formed at a faster rate than the growth of the nuclei so it gives a uniform and reduced grain size coating. At 60° C and above, we observed burnt and irregular deposits. So we have fixed 50° as the optimum temperature for our studies.

3.3.1.4 Duty Cycle

The deposition was performed at 25, 50 and 75% duty cycles in the PC method and by DC method. In the DC method, coating morphology was not uniform and with higher grain size compared to the PC method. In the PC method coating obtained at 75% is more uniform with reduced grain size was observed compared to 25% and 50% coating. In the PC method, fresh nuclei were formed and it produces uniform and reduced grain coatings during ON and OFF time of the current. In 25% and 50%, the grain size was almost the same as the DC method.

In the DC method, nucleic are formed and the growth of the same nuclei forms a bigger grain size. In our studies, the PC method at 75% duty cycle produces a bright, uniform and small grain size coating compared to other methods.

Table 3.1 Optimized bath composition

Composition	Parameters range
Platinum Solution [Pt (NH ₃) ₂] HPO ₄	0.15 ml
Temperature	55°C
pH	10.5
Current density	2.5 A/dm ²
Deposition time	12 min
Duty cycle	75%

3.4 Coatings Characterisation

3.4.1 Surface Morphology

Fig. 3.1. SEM images of Platinum coated samples: 75% duty cycle (a), 50% duty cycle (b), 25% duty cycle (c) and DC (d)

SEM images were captured to know the surface morphology of the platinum-coated samples. In our Experimental part, 2.5 A/dm² give good covering power with a better appearance. So we have taken this one that has optimum current density for our studies.

Fig. 3.1 shows SEM images of platinum-coated samples. Platinum coated by PC method at 75% duty cycle shows uniform with reduced grain size and less porosity. This tendency was decreased in 50% and 25% duty cycle samples. High irregular coating with a bigger crystal size was observed in the DC method sample. In the PC method during OFF time, the nucleation mechanism was stopped and ON time again fresh nucleic are formed. In this way, the grain size was reduced in the PC method and particularly at 75% duty cycle. In 25% and 50%, bath parameters are not entertaining to give the reduced grain size [35]. By comparing all the SEM images, coatings obtained by 75% duty cycle is more uniform bright, non-porous and crystalline in nature.

3.4.2 EDX-Studies

The elemental composition of Pt deposited on SS304 was measured by EDX in Fig. 3.2. The stainless steel surface was cleaner and free from significant imperfections after the polishing process since the abrasives removed small amounts of metal. The removal of contaminants and oxide layer allows for deposition and improves the coating adhesion to the substrate. To establish the existence of elements on the steel substrate after coating platinum metal ions by PC method at 75% duty cycle and 2.5 A/dm^2 , An EDX study was performed, and the platinum metal ions with the highest percentage in the coating was confirmed and listed in Table 3.2.

Fig. 3.2. EDX analysis of the platinum

Table 3.2 Elemental compositions of the stainless steel substrate after platinum coating (PC 75% duty cycle)

Elements	Pt	C	Mn	P	Cr	Ni	Si	S	Fe
SS304	--	0.08	2.00	0.045	18.0-20.0	8.0-12.0	0.75	0.030	Balance
SS304 After Coating Pt	42.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	8.03	2.05	0.0	0.0	24.74

3.4.3 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

The surface morphologies of platinum electrodeposition on SS304 have been discovered to back up the findings of other research methods according to AFM examinations. AFM was used to determine the average roughness of the platinum coatings, as indicated in Table 3.3. Figure 3.3 shows 3D images of platinum coatings created using the DC and PC methods. Surface roughness is lower in coatings generated by the PC technique at 75% duty cycle than in other samples. The result of the SEM pictures in Fig. 3.3 was attributed to this finding. The smaller grain size for the PC sample obtained at 75% duty cycle results in a lower roughness. As a consequence of the foregoing investigation, the roughness of the coatings increases as the size of the crystalline grain increases. The surface morphology of their crystallite measurements is significantly affected by duty cycle variation. Dye degradation increased when platinum grain size decreased [36]. The photocatalytic activity indicates the presence of two opposing influences that happen whenever the average grain size falls and the active surface area increases (which promotes high photocatalytic activity) [37]. The effective surface area of the SS304 working electrode was found to be 1.46 cm² by using 0.006 mol platinum 5Q-bath and diffusion coefficient 0.298 × 10⁻⁶ cm² s⁻¹ (Randles-Sevcik equation) [38].

Table 3.3 The average roughness of the platinum coatings

Specimen	DC	PC25%	PC 50%	PC75%
Average roughness(nm)	4.2701	3.6289	3.4666	3.4191

Fig. 3.3 3D figures representing the roughness of (a) DC (b) PC 25% (c) PC 50% and (d) PC 75%

3.5 Photocatalytic studies

Developed Platinum coated samples were used for dye degradation containing MB by photocatalysis method. Methylene blue ($C_{16}H_{18}N_3SCl$) is a phenothiazine derivative that is a heterocyclic aromatic azo-dye with a cation whose molecular structure is given in Fig. 3.4. The MB solution was prepared by using double distilled water and processed in the dark. Visible annular photoreactor (Agilent technology Cary-60) used for photocatalytic studies purchased from the scientific company "HEBER," Chennai, India. The cylinder reactor is made up of a central light source surrounded by eight reactor tubing (each with a capacity of 100mL) and cooled by fans in the photoreactor. SS304 was coated with platinum metal using a PC and DC technique with varied current densities and duty cycles. The photocatalytic performance of all of these samples was investigated.

The obtained samples were examined for the degradation of MB by UV light irradiation. No changes in the color of the dye at the beginning in dark light. Degradation of the dye initiated after interaction with light. Charge carriers will start migrating and leading to reduction of oxygen and forming peroxides and superoxides. Hydroxyl radicals are formed from the oxidation of water obtained from holes and it was represented in Figure 3.5. Dye degradation

and additionally removal of byproducts from made radicals which are highly reactive and unstable.

Fig. 3.4 Molecular structure of Methylene Blue

Fig. 3.5 Proposed mechanism

While the MB dye was destroyed in the presence of a photocatalyst, the absorption peak at 664 nm steadily reduced. Cationic (MB) dye degradation has reached 99%, 97%, 95% and 96% for PC 75%, PC 50%, PC 25% and DC coated samples respectively as shown in Fig. 3.6. Table 3.4 gives complete information on dye degradation efficiency of different samples obtained by electrodeposition.

In our work, we have achieved good degradation by Platinum coated sample by PC method at 75% duty cycle compared to DC coated sample or other samples. This may be due to the smaller grain size of the sample. The increase in effluent load on catalyst increases the number of photons absorbed on its surface and increases the OH and e^-/h^+ pairs. PC coated sample with 75% duty cycle gives good efficiency because of this reason.

Pure platinum wire with 3.8 cm length and 0.5 mm thickness was used for the dye degradation for the same duration. It gives 35% dye degradation efficiency. The prepared

samples are very cheap compared to pure platinum metal and also gives more dye degradation efficiency.

Electrodeposited platinum on SS304 is a good photocatalyst material for the cationic (MB) dye degradation, as evidenced by the improved findings, the synergetic effect, and also by the aforementioned analysis.

Table 3.4 Efficiency of Methylene blue dye degradation by different samples

PC 75%	PC 50%	PC 25%	DC
99%	97%	95%	96%

Fig. 3.6 Percentage degradation of MB dye with a run time

3.6 Factors affecting dye degradations

3.6.1 Effects of dye concentrations

The absorption of color determines how quickly it degrades when exposed to light. As the dye concentration increased, the catalyst's activity reduced. To identify the best color concentration, the 100 ml sample was used for the analysis, over 5 ppm, 10 ppm, 15 ppm, and 20 ppm dye concentrations, as shown in Fig. 3.7. This is determined by the concentration of dye molecules on the catalytic surface, which lowers the level of light penetration through the catalyst, reducing dye degradation. The formation rate of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals was found to be lower as a result of this 5 ppm solution demonstrates more photocatalytic

degradation than a higher concentration of dye (10–20 ppm) and degradation efficacy is listed in Table 3.5.

Table 3.5 Studies of photocatalytic dye degradation efficiency in terms of different MB dye concentrations.

Coating Source	5 ppm	10 ppm	15 ppm	20 ppm
Pt 75%	99%	79%	66%	57%

Fig. 3.7 Photocatalytic activities of MB dye at different dye concentrations concerning PC 75% duty cycle.

3.6.2 Effect of hydrogen potential (pH)

One of the significant factors broadly alter photocatalytic degradation is pH. 5 ppm MB dye solution was put through its paces of degradation of dye by using Platinum coated sample at 75% duty cycle in various pH ranges from 2 to 12. Fig. 3.8 indicates that photocatalytic activity increases with an increase in the solution's pH. The outside surface area of platinum-coated metal samples has a positive charge in acidic conditions and is negatively charged at basic pH. Because MB is a cationic dye and platinum has a negative charge, the electrostatic interaction of a negatively charged surface with cationic methylene blue causes deterioration. In the basic media, the availability of OH⁻ is increased, which speeds up the dye degradation process. Table 3.6 indicates platinum coated sample by 75% duty cycle gives higher dye degradation activities compare to the rest of the coated samples.

Table 3.6 Studies of photocatalytic activity of the platinum coated sample in different pH.

Coating Source	2 pH	4 pH	6 pH	8 pH	10 pH	12 pH
Pt 75%	54%	67%	72%	80%	86%	99%

Fig. 3.8 Photocatalytic activities of MB dye at different pH concerning Pt -75%

3.6.3 Scavenger studies

Scavenger research has looked into the active factors that cause pollutants to degrade. During the photocatalytic degradation process under UV light, hydrogen ions, electrons, and superoxide anions (oxygen species) are generated. Tertiary butyl alcohol (TBA) for hydroxide \cdot , EDTA (Ethylene diamine tetraacetic acid) for hydrogen ion (H^+), $K_2Cr_2O_7$ for electrons anions (OH and Ascorbic Acid (AA) for oxygen species like anion scavengers were added to dyes separately conduct the scavenger experiment. Fig. 3.9 shows the photodegradation of MB dyes catalyzed by platinum-coated by 75% duty cycle under UV light source in the presence and absence of scavengers. It is concluded that hydroxide anion is the most reactive species and is primarily responsible for MB dye degradation.

Fig. 3.9 Effect of scavengers on PC 75% of MB dye

3.6.4 Reusability and stability

The key concerns in photocatalytic degradation in platinum electrodeposition are stability and recovery. After deterioration (cycle 1), platinum coated samples were rinsed with distilled water to remove adsorbed dye molecules on the photocatalyst's surface, platinum-coated samples were rinsed with distilled water, then water molecules were removed in a hot air oven. The dried samples were used in the recovery and stability experiment, which was carried out over four deterioration cycles. The photocatalyst's reusability efficiency declined from 99% (1st cycle) to 88% (4th cycle) after four cycles, as illustrated in **Fig. 3.10**. Even after the fourth degrading cycle, the photocatalyst activity was reduced by 11% efficiency. Under a visible light source, the recovered catalyst can be employed to degrade dyes further [39-40].

Fig. 3.10 Stability of the Platinum coated sample with different cycles

3.7 Conclusions

The platinum metal was coated on SS4304 successfully by DC and PC method. All the coatings were characterized by SEM and EDX. SEM results indicate that PC coated samples with 75% duty cycles have the least grain size compared to other samples and particularly DC coated samples. AFM tests confirm that the roughness of the coating is lower in the 75% duty cycle. The prepared samples were effectively used for MB dye degradation by the photocatalysis method. PC coated with a 75% duty cycle gives 99% efficiency. Even after four cycles, the stability and reusability were found to be very strong.

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CHAPTER – 4

Application in hydrogen generation: Platinum electrodeposition

4.1 Introduction

Despite being one of the fastest electrocatalytic reactions, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) requires high platinum loadings (0.5–1.0 mg/cm²). It requires optimization of the extent of catalyst loading in order to reduce the cost of the electrode. Redox reactions at electrode and solution interfaces are becoming increasingly important in modern science and technology, as they decide the efficiency of a variety of electrochemical devices to be used in the future for sustainable renewable energy [1-5]. Efficiencies of electrolyzers and fuel cells are mainly determined by the effectiveness of interface between catalytic electrodes and electrolytes [6-11]. However by using latest technology and art, only around 4% of hydrogen is produced from water electrolysis [12-14]. It is mainly due to lack of design of the electrodes that leads to less production of hydrogen with high over voltage leading to high energy loss. In producing 15 trillion moles of hydrogen per year (4%), the average price is EUR 0.1kWh in the US and Europe [15-17]. These costs of production are higher than that for production of hydrogen using noble metal as catalysts. By using the proper knowledge in noble metal coating, production of hydrogen is economically viable method [18-19]. The amount of platinum on the coating is very important parameter and by using proper knowledge small amount platinum in the coating reduces the cost effect and gives the highest amount of hydrogen gas.

In this proposed work, Platinum metal was coated by DC and PC method with minimum load of 0.5µg/cm². All these deposits were analyzed by SEM, AFM and XRD. Linear sweep voltammetry, Tafel polarization, cyclic voltammetry studies and Chronopotentiometry experiments were conducted to know hydrogen generation behavior of these coatings.

4.2 Materials and method

4.2.1 Plating of Platinum by Electrodeposition method

Platinum 5Q plating solution was used in the present study was supplied by Arora Matthey Limited, Kolkata. The Q bath is based on the complex [Pt (NH₃)₄] HPO₄ in phosphate buffer at a pH, 10.5. Electroplating bath was twenty times diluted solution of the original solution. The solution pH was adjusted using 10% NaOH. All voltammetry experiments and electrodepositions were performed at 50 ± 1 °C using CH 608D Electrochemical workstation. Circular shape cathodes with 15 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness made by SS304 were used to coated platinum. The samples were mechanically polished (METCO polishing machine, Chennai made, India) to get a mirror finish. Table 4.1 gives the optimized bath composition.

The amount of platinum coated after electrodeposition process was calculated by knowing the weights of cathode specimens before and after the experiment.

Table 4.1 Optimized bath Composition

Components	Parameters
Platinum Solution [Pt (NH ₃) ₂] HPO ₄	0.2 g/l
Temperature	50°C
pH	10.5
Current density	2.5 A/dm ²
Deposition time	12 min
Duty cycle	DC method and 25%,50%75%

4.2.2 Coatings' characterization.

Scanning electron microscopy was used to know the surface morphology of the coatings before and after electroplating. SEM pictures of platinum coated materials were acquired using a 5.00 kV and 15 kV scanning electron microscope (model: FESEM Carl ZEISS), 3.7 mm average wide distance at different magnifications. X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained using Rigaku Miniflex 600 (5th gen) diffractometer. Atomic force microscopic images (Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM & STM) were obtained to know the surface morphologies of coated samples. Surface morphological properties for both coated and naked samples were examined for comparison.

4.2.3 Electrochemical studies

Electrodeposited platinum electrodes were subjected to cathodic and anodic polarization in the cell, which was used to measure the amount of hydrogen liberated during the experiment. The working electrode was electrodeposited platinum coatings, and the counter electrode were a platinum electrode with the same surface area. As a reference electrode, Ag/AgCl was used. Electrochemical behavior of the coatings was evaluated by cyclic voltammetry, Tafel polarization, linear sweep voltammetry and chronopotentiometry studies in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ medium, using computer controlled compactostat.h 10800 from Ivium Technologies, Netherlands. A graduated gas collector was installed in the cell, with the liberated hydrogen replacing a corresponding amount of solution. This facility gave the amount of hydrogen liberated during the experiment. The schematic diagram of the setup is given in Fig.4.1.

Fig. 4.1 Schematic diagram of tubular three-electrode glass cell used to measure the electro catalytic activity of the platinum metal electrodeposit in terms of H_2/O_2 released gas on the surface of electrode.

4.3 Results and Discussion

4.3.1 Electrodeposition

Platinum metal was coated on SS 304 by optimizing all the parameters like, bath composition, pH, current density, temperature and time of coating. Amount of platinum coated after electrodeposition was estimated by taking the difference in weight of the cathode specimen before and after coating. Around $0.5\mu g/cm^2$ was coated on the sample obtained by 75% duty cycle sample.

4.4 Coatings characterizations

4.4.1 SEM studies

To understand the surface morphology of the platinum-coated samples, SEM images were captured. We found that $2.5 A/dm^2$ of current density offers better dispersity of platinum metal atoms forming a seemingly porous on the surface. This current density is considered as the optimum current density for our tests because the resulting electrode is the one with best performance towards HER with minimum amount of platinum. In Fig. 4.2 we show the SEM images of the coatings obtained by PC and DC methods with different duty cycle. We found platinum ions dispersity more and more and covering the entire portion of surfaces in subsequent duty cycles like 50%, 25%. The direct current coated samples are crystalline in nature and uniform in size. In 25%, sample coating was more uniform as also found in DC coated sample. Coatings obtained at 75% duty cycle are not as uniform as the 25% and 50% samples. Coatings with a parallelogram like structure with a width of 20 nm and a length of 100 nm were observed in 75% sample. Samples obtained by the DC method are more

uniform compared PC coated samples. By comparing all the coatings images, we conclude that, 75% duty cycle coatings are more uneven, porous, non-uniform and bright in nature. Coatings obtained by 75% duty cycle are crystalline and must be more cost effective.

Fig. 4.2 SEM images of Platinum coated on SS304. (A) 75% duty cycle (B) 50% duty cycle (C) 25% duty cycle (D) DC.

4.4.2 AFM studies

AFM studies show that the surface morphologies of SS304 platinum-coated specimens agree with the SEM. Table 4.2 gives the average roughness of the platinum coatings as assessed by AFM. 3D images of platinum coating by DC, PC with different duty cycle are shown in Fig. 4.3. The 75% duty cycle sample obtained by PC method shows diminished roughness compared to other specimens. This result agrees with to the result of the SEM images. Samples with lower grain size show increased roughness. The variation in the duty cycle by PC method seems to strongly influence the crystallinity and morphology of platinum deposits.

Fig. 4.3 AFM images of (a) DC (b) PC 25% (c) PC 50% (d) PC 75% samples

Table 4.2 The average roughness of the platinum coatings

Specimen	Mean (S_m ; f_m)	Valley depth (S_v ; nm)	Peak height (S_p ; nm)	Peak valley height (S_y ; nm)	Average roughness (S_a ; nm)	Root mean square roughness (S_q) (nm)
DC	5 μ m	-20.231	66.861	87.092	5.3314	8.8114
25%	5 μ m	-25.821	74.581	100.4	4.2701	6.7417
50%	5 μ m	-29.319	22.237	51.556	3.4666	4.5617
75%	5 μ m	-16.492	30.396	46.889	3.4191	4.6658

4.4.3 XRD studies.

Fig. 4.4 The XRD pattern of Platinum coating obtained at DC and PC 75%.

XRD (Fig 4.4) shows patterns of electrodeposited platinum on SS304 from the solution investigated for Pulse coating. These XRD pattern show that crystalline film of platinum with orientations (111), (200), (220), (311), and (222) with face-centered cubic (FCC) structure (JCPDS database No. 04-0802).

4.5 Electro catalytic activity for HER

4.5.1 Linear Sweep Voltammetry

Fig. 4.5 Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) curves for HER on the surface of the platinum coatings in 0.5M H₂SO₄ acidic solution.

To evaluate the HER performance of the platinum coated samples, LSVs were performed in 0.5 M H₂SO₄. Fig. 4.5 shows the LSV of pure Pt and Pt coated SS: It reveals almost zero over potential value for pure Pt for HER. In the same way, Pt coated on steel also shows value of HER potential [20]. The HER performance of DC coated Pt catalysts is inferior to that of the Pt coated by PC method. The performance of Pt coated by 75% duty cycle is better than the 25% and 50% duty cycle deposited Pt. Here, we have achieved the highest current density of 150 mA/cm² at 0.24 and 0.25V for pure Pt and Pt coated on steel by PC (75% duty cycle), respectively. This is attributed to the fact that, coatings obtained at 75% duty cycle are having smooth and small grain size compared to other coatings. Increased effective surface area is the main reason for getting good hydrogen generation efficiency of 75% sample. Hydrogen evolution increase with increasing corrosion current of the coatings.

To investigate further the catalytic mechanism for the HER process, Tafel plots were constructed as shown in the Fig. 4.6. It is known that HER mechanism follows Volmer–Heyrovsky step if the Tafel slope is near to 120 mV per dec, HER mechanism follows

Volmer–Tafel steps if the slope is nearly 30 mV per dec which implies that smaller the Tafel slope faster is the reaction rate [21].

Fig. 4.6 Tafel plots for various electrodes in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

Table 4.3 Tafel slopes

Si No	Platinum electrode sample	Tafel slope mV/dec
01	Pure platinum	38
02	DC	61
03	75%	30
04	50%	67
05	25%	80

The Tafel slope was found to be 30mV/dec, 67 mV/dec and 80 mV/dec for the Pt coated by 75% duty cycle, 50% duty cycle and 25% duty cycle, respectively. In Table 4.3, the Tafel slope of Pt coated by 75% duty cycle is much smaller than that for the Pt coated by DC method (61 mV/dec). Smaller slope of 30 mV/dec indicates that the Tafel step is the rate determining step and that HER takes place according to the Volmer–Tafel steps on Pt coated by 75% duty cycle. 75% coated sample has more porous and low roughness values and it is the main reason for getting good hydrogen evolution compare to other samples.

4.5.2 Chronopotentiometry.

The easiest way to assess stability against electro catalytic operation is to use a chronopotentiometry experiment to evaluate the potential of the coated samples in constant current with time. Constant current method was adopted to know the hydrogen generation on coated samples by Chronopotentiometry analysis. Stability is an important parameter to evaluate whether the catalyst has the potential for use in hydrogen generation in practical applications. The typical methods for characterizing the stability of electrocatalysts is chronopotentiometry. Here, we measure the potential change with time at a fixed current. For this measurement, the longer the tested potential remains constant, the better is the stability of the catalyst. The nature of chronopotentiograms for platinum coatings are provided in Fig. 4.7. The stability of the Pt coated electrodes are excellent and comparable to that of the pure Pt metal. The amount of hydrogen collected for 150 seconds for different samples are given in Fig. 4.8.

Fig. 4.7 Chronopotentiometry curves recorded for the platinum coatings

Fig. 4.8 Volume of H₂ evolved in 150 seconds

4.5.3 Tafel Measurements

To evaluate the suitability of the developed electrode for hydrogen generation application, the electrochemical stability of the electrode was investigated using a potentiodynamic polarization study. The corrosion behavior of these samples was studied by Tafel plots in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ medium. Fig. 4.9 shows that the Tafel curves for pure Platinum, DC and PC coated samples. Corrosion current is 0.008021A/cm² and 0.005473A/cm² for sample obtained by PC (75% duty cycle) method and DC method respectively. More corrosion current indicates maximum hydrogen evolution in the medium. Cathodic slope value for PC sample coated at 75% duty cycle is -0.116 v/dec and -0.221 v/dec for DC coated sample. Sample coated at 75% duty cycle by PC method has smaller cathodic slope compare to DC coated sample. Also the sample obtained at 25% and 50% by PC method shows small cathodic slope values as given in the Table 4.4. Platinum coated samples are having very good catalytic activity to generate hydrogen gas and it behaves similar to pure platinum metal. Here a cost-effective, very thin layer of platinum is coated by electrodeposition method with around 0.5 μg/cm². In these coatings, very small quantity of platinum was coated to achieve the hydrogen generation similar to pure platinum. Pure platinum metal and Platinum coated by PC method at 75% duty cycle shows same trend in Tafel measurements indicating that, these coating are having small amount of platinum on the surface of steel which mimics the properties of pure platinum.

Table 4.4 The Electrochemical data obtained in Tafel measurements

Type of sample	I corr A	E corr V	β_c v/dec
75%	0.008021	-0.3219	0.116
50%	0.007664	-0.3252	0.198
25%	0.008001	-0.3266	0.201
DC	0.005473	-0.3238	0.221
Pure Platinum	0.007597	-0.3227	0.118

Fig. 4.9 Potentiodynamic polarization curves of Platinum coatings

4.6 Conclusions

Platinum was coated on SS304 by Electrodeposition method with $0.5\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ platinum load. Coatings obtained by PC method at 75% duty cycle shows crystallinity, shigh porosity with less roughness. Developed Platinum coatings show same trend similar to that of pure platinum towards HER. These coatings are economical and maybe used for commercial applications.

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CHAPTER – 5

**Application in photocatalytic
dye degradation:
Platinum - Rhodium alloy
electrodeposition**

5.1 Introduction

Platinum, palladium, rhodium, ruthenium, iridium, and osmium are members of the platinum group metals (PGM). Only platinum, palladium, and rhodium have previously found significant use in the electrodeposited condition [1]. The main disadvantage of this alloy coating is its high cost; however, its benefits include excellent chemical and oxidation resistance, as well as high strength, the main resistance to corrosion at high temperatures, are present in different areas such as the production of glass [2,3] and nitrogen fertilizers [4,5,6], thermocouples [7], automotive catalysts [9], jewellery [9,10] etc.

Pulse Electrodeposition is considered a more efficient method of Electroplating compare to the DC method of Electrodeposition. In the PC method, based on the required current can be controlled by the ON and OFF method. In ON time current is passed into the time it is switched off. During OFF time more time will be given to nucleation and which reduces the nuclei size and give the uniform crystalline size. We value PC over DC in Pt-Rh alloy coating because electroplating of Pt-Rh by DC consumes a major amount of metal ions from the bath solution, resulting in the poor coating. The PC plating technique, on the other hand, would be extremely beneficial in that have noticeably reduced the amount of Pt-Rh consumed during plating which may find various industrial applications. As a result, production costs will be lower, production time will be shorter, and coating quality will improve [11]. Also, conventionally DC plating only one parameter, namely, the current density can be varied. However, the PC method has three important factors: peak current density, current ON time and current OFF time can be varied and growth can be controlled [12].

Noble metal coatings were done on stainless steel to control the corrosion in boiler water reactors. Intergranular corrosion is very common in boilers. So the development of noble metal coatings on stainless steel with high corrosion resistance is very important in boilers. Noble metal chemical addition is a recent development in this field and it reduces corrosion abruptly. Many methods are available to coat Noble metal on the steel surface. Electrodeposition is a simple and efficient method for coating Noble metals. In this technique, noble metal can be coated uniformly [13].

Rhodamine-B (RhB) is used by several nano metal oxides for dye degradation of ZrCo₂ doped lead dioxide nanocomposites [14]. Hydrothermally synthesised CeO₂ doped TiO₂ nanocomposites had a photodegradation efficiency of 98.89% when exposed to RhB UV induced sunlight [15]. Evaluation of UV/visible light induced removal of organic dye from

urban waste water using La_2O_3 garlanded ceria hetero structured binary metal oxide nano plates [16]. Under UV irradiation, synthesised nano – TiO_2 appears to be a good photocatalyst for the purification and reuse of coloured aqueous effluents [17]. Zea mays L. dry husk mediated bio-synthesized copper oxide nanoparticles utilised MB as dye and had a 91% degradation efficiency [18]. After 240 minutes of degradation, hierarchical yttria nanosphere decorated ceria nanorods demonstrated an efficiency of 95.8 % [19]. Under visible light irradiation, a $\text{Sm}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ heterojunction photocatalyst was employed to efficiently degrade Rhodamine-B dye with waste water [20].

Roughly 8–20 % of idle dyes and auxiliary chemicals are settled from the textile production into the wastewater stream [21]. Nearly one million tons of dyes are made every year around the biosphere. Furthermore, the majority of these dyes and their components are carcinogenic and mutagenic, posing a threat to all living things on the planet [22, 23, 24]. Even a small amount (less than 1 ppm) of these compounds in water has negative consequences [25]. The excellent corrosion resistant properties of Pt-Rh catalysts are evaluated for the gradation of dyes. In this work, Pt-Rh coated samples successfully showed positive trends in the degradation of Methylene Blue (MB) dye.

5.2 Materials and Methods

5.2.1 Electrodeposition Development

The solution used in the present study was Pt 5Q electroplating bath $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{HPO}_4$ and Rhodium Sulphate solution $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ supplied by Arora Matthey Limited, Kolkata. The electrolyte solution was prepared using 1.5 mL Platinum solution and 0.075 mL Rhodium solution. By adding 5 ml concentrated H_2SO_4 and distilled water, this solution is made to 50 ml. The experiment was carried out in a glass cell Fig. 5.1. Pt-Rh alloy coatings with a 1.7 cm^2 exposed surface area were formed on SS304. To achieve a smooth finish, abrading 600 grade to 2500 emery paper was used to prepare polished SS304 surfaces and after that, alumina powder is used to polish the surface (1.0, then 0.3 and 0.05 μm grades) on a humid polishing cloth, then thoroughly cleaned with deionized water. Only emery paper abrading and washing were used to prepare rough surfaces. Freshly machined SS304 discs were used in one set of experiments, and they will have the tool marks from their fabrication on a lathe.

The cathode is made of SS304 circular discs with a diameter of 15 mm and a thickness of 1 mm and at a distance of 2 mm from the coupon's edge, a 2 mm hole was provided to hold the disc during electrodeposition [26]. While coating process the remaining portion of the backside was masked. The anode was made of platinized titanium. Electrodeposition was

carried out for 18 minutes using a current source N6705B Key sight technologies of direct current (DC) and pulse current (PC) for a range of cathodic current densities ranging from 1.0 to 6.0 A/dm². pH and temperature are kept at 1.2 and 40 °C, respectively. The coatings were carefully rinsed with distilled water after each deposition and then air-dried.

Fig. 5.1 Schematic representation of pulse electrodeposition of platinum on SS304.

Table 5.1 Improved component's bath solution

Components	Conformation
Platinum solution $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{HPO}_4$	1.5 ml
Rhodium sulphate solution $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	0.075 ml
H_2SO_4	5 ml
Electrodeposition Bound	
Heat	40 °C
pH	1.2
Current density	4.0 A/dm ²
Installation time	18 min
PC Duty cycle	25%, 50 % and 75%
DC	Direct current flow

The surface morphology and compositional analysis of the formed coatings were studied using scanning electron microscopy (FESEM Carl ZEISS). The phase structure and crystallite grain size were examined using X-ray diffraction (XRD, RIGAKU).

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and the Tafel extrapolation technique was used to assess the corrosion behaviour of Pt-Rh alloy Electrodeposition by a three-electrode system, using a CHI608D electrochemical workstation (CH Instruments, Austin, USA) to keep open to air at room temperature. The Ag/AgCl electrode and the platinum electrode, respectively, were used as reference and counter electrodes. The EIS study was conducted on an electrodeposited coated working electrode with an exposed surface area of 1 cm^2 in 0.1M sodium sulphate as corrosive media in neutral pH

Photocatalytic experiments were carried out in the centre of the cylindrical photoreactor, which consists of a light source (here, a UV light lamp, 300 W, absorbance at 664 nm (UV-Vis absorption spectra)) surrounded by eight quartz reactor tubes (each 100 mL in volume), 37 cm in height and 2.3 cm in inner diameter, as well as cooling fans. A reaction mixture consisting of a catalytic load of different electrodeposited Pt-Rh alloy coated samples with two different current sources, namely DC and PC, with 25%, 50% and 75% respectively, was prepared in 100 ml of 5 ppm MB dye. The suspension was stirred in the dark for 3 hours. The solution was irradiated under UV light at a constant temperature. Samples were also collected every 30 minutes to evaluate the percentage of MB degradation. A visible annular photoreactor (Agilent technology Cary-60) was purchased from the scientific company "HEBER" in Chennai, India for use in photocatalytic studies. The MB solution was prepared in the dark using double distilled water. A central light source powers the cylinder reactor. Surrounded by eight reactor tubing (each with a capacity of 100mL) and cooled by fans in the photoreactor. The Pt-Rh alloy metal coating was done on SS304 using a PC and DC technique with different duty cycles, and the maximum dye degradation was selected from the metal coating and further degradation parameter work was done only for the respective sample. All of these samples were tested for photocatalytic performance.

The percentage of photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes has been determined as follows.

$$\% \text{ of degradation} = [(C_a - C_b) / C_a] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{equation -1}$$

Where C_a and C_b is initial and final dye concentration respectively. The research was repeated by a selection of parameters, such as dye concentration, stability, scavengers and pH.

5.3 Results and Discussions

5.3.1 Optimization of Bath Parameters

The electrodeposition method was used to deposit Pt-Rh coatings on mild steel panels using the optimized electrolytic bath listed in Table 5.1. To obtain a good, desirable coating, pH, temperature, current density, and composition of the bath plays a crucial role in the evaluation of the coating.

When it comes to achieving the best electrodeposition coating, the current density is crucial. The current density was varied from 1.0 A/dm² to 10.0 A/dm² to determine the effect of the coating. The formation of a "burnt" black colour deposit occurred at current densities greater than 5 A/dm² due to rapid discharge of metal ions from the electrolyte resulting in poor coating and Metal ions deposition is a smaller amount at current densities less than 4.0 A/dm², uneven and irregular deposition on the substrate occurs and hence in our research, a current density of 4.0 A/cm² has been determined to be optimal.

The alloy coating was carried out at the ideal temperature of 40 °C by DC and PC method by making the variation in an optimized condition. At 40 °C, the electrolyte dissociates, even more, resulting in the highest concentration of metal ions in the bath solution and a uniform coating. In comparison to other temperatures, coating at 40 °C produces a bright and adherent coating. At temperatures of 50 °C and higher, we discovered burnt and unusual deposits. The coating obtained below 40 °C provides a seedy appearance due to an uneven coating. As a result, we have decided to test at a temperature of 40 °C.

The pH of the alloy coatings was varied from 0.10 to 3.0, and pH 1.3 was found to be the best, with the majority of the metal ions deposited at this pH. The stability of the bath deteriorated at higher pH values above 2.0, and burnt deposits formed. The coatings were smooth, uniform, and bright at a range from pH 1.0 to 1.5, but the coatings were poor at pH less than 1.0 so more research was done at pH around 1.0 to 2.0.

At 25, 50, and 75 % duty cycles, the deposition was finished using both the DC and PC systems. When compared to the PC method with a larger grain size obtained from DC, the coating morphology in the DC method was not uniform. The coating obtained at 75 % in the PC method is more even and regular, with smaller grain size. In the PC method, fresh nuclei were formed and it produces uniform and reduced grain coatings during ON and OFF time of the current. The grain size difference is marginal when compared to DC, 25% and 50% duty cycle. In comparison to other methods, the PC-75% method produces bright, uniform, and small grain sizes.

5.4 Coatings Characterizations

5.4.1 Scanning electron microscope

SEM images were obtained using 5.00 kV and 15.0 kV scanning electron microscope (model: FESEM Carl ZEISS) with a mean large gap of 3.7 mm at different magnifications. SEM images of coatings obtained from PCs with various duty cycles and DC plating developed at current density $4.0\text{A}/\text{dm}^2$ as shown in Fig. 5.2. When compared to the remaining PCs and DC source in (Figure 5.4.1.2 a) 75 % duty cycle coating, the smaller and uniform grains result in a smoother surface of the coatings. From Figures 5.4.1.2 b, c and d, the Pt-Rh alloy was found to be larger and uneven in scale on SS304 and its distribution is not uniform. In DC coating samples, the degree of uniformity decreased as the duty cycle percent decreased from 75 % to 25 % and more. The percent of duty cycle has a significant effect on the surface morphology of Pt-Rh electroplated coatings, as shown in Figures 5.4.1.2 a, b, c and d. For all the Pt-Rh alloy coating sources, strong adhesion and brightness were obtained, but in a 75 % duty cycle uniformity was achieved.

Fig. 5.2 Surface morphology of Pt-Rh deposits produced at PC conditions. (a) 75% (b) 50% (c) 25%, (d) DC.

5.4.2 Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy

The EDX analysis (Model: Oxford Instrument 250) was used to determine the presence of metal ions on the substrate by electrodeposition techniques. The percentage of Pt and Rh on the coating is also justified by EDX. According to the EDX analysis in Figure 5.3, Pt inclusion was greater than Rh inclusion because the concentration of Pt was higher in the bath than Rh. This coating variation explains why the Pt contribution to dye degradation was greater than the Rh.

Fig. 5.3 EDX study for Pt-Rh alloy coating at PC 75% duty cycle.

5.4.3 X-ray diffraction

Fig. 5.4 The XDR pattern of Pt-Rh coating was obtained at DC and PC (25%, 50% and 75%).

X-ray diffraction (Rigaku Miniflex 600 (5th gen)) was used to obtain patterns of X-ray diffractometers. The XRD pattern of Pt-Rh coating electrodeposited on stainless steel by DC and PC (25%, 50% and 75%) method are as shown in Fig. 5.4. The peaks were analyzed by crystallographic search match software using powder diffraction files PDF numbers: 87-644 Pt(H-loaded) syn, 1-1190 Pt, 34-529 Fe, 1-1267 Fe, 65-6840 Fe₃Rh₇ and 2-1167 Fe Pt. The diffraction pattern mainly includes Pt peaks corresponding to planes (111), (200), (311) and (222) and these Pt phases contain a smaller amount of Rh. The peaks Pt (111) and Pt (200) are search matched from powder diffraction PDF number 87-644 Pt. Further the peaks Pt (311) and Pt (222) are search matched from powder diffraction PDF number 1-1190 Pt. Further base metal stainless steel (Fe) and Fe-Pt peaks are also observed on XRD pattern. The intensity of Fe peaks reduces in 75% PC coating. Indicate that during 75% PC plating surface of the stainless surface was uniformly covered with Pt-Rh coating. The XRD peaks corresponding to Rh is not found in DC, 25% and 75% PC plated coating while 50% PC coating contain (3110) Fe₃Rh₇ peak (65-6840 Fe₃Rh₇). The line broadening is observed in peak corresponding to Pt confirms fine grained nature of the Pt coating deposited on steel surface. Rhodium peak was not observed in the spectra and it is because of small quantity of rhodium in the coating. The crystallite size analysis was made using the Debye Scherrer method on (111) diffraction peak. In PC (75%) crystallite size was reduced compared to DC plating.

The Scherrer equation can be written as:

$$L = \frac{K \lambda}{\beta \cos \theta}$$

Where L is the crystallite size (nm), β is the full width half maximum intensity measured in radians, λ is the X-ray wavelength, θ is the diffraction angle and K is the Scherrer constant (0.95). Average crystalline size is listed in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. Average crystalline size.

SI No	Source of coating	Average crystalline size in nm
01	PC- 75 %	10
02	PC- 50 %	07
03	PC- 25 %	06
04	DC	05

5.5 Electrochemical measurements

5.5.1 Potentiodynamic polarization study

Fig. 5.5 Potentiodynamic polarization curves of the Platinum-Rhodium coatings.

Table 5.3 Corrosion data obtained from potentiodynamic polarization method.

Coating source	$-E_{\text{corr}}$ (V vs SCE)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$)	βa (V/dec)	βc (V/dec)	C.R. (mil/yr)
PC 75%	0.019	4.658	4.893	5.749	2.126
PC 50%	0.098	6.431	4.544	5.182	2.935
PC 25%	0.096	7.472	4.945	5.587	3.410
Direct Current	0.076	6.238	4.535	5.331	2.847

The corrosion behavior of the Pt-Rh metal coating developed on SS304 was studied using the potentiodynamic polarization method, Fig.5.5. The coatings were created at 4.5A/dm^2 and then tested in a $0.1\text{M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution. Table 5.3 summarizes the resulting corrosion parameters such as corrosion current (i_{corr}), corrosion potential (E_{corr}) and corrosion rate (CR). Coatings obtained at 75% duty cycle shows the least corrosion current ($4.658\ \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$) and highest positive potential ($-0.019\ E_{\text{corr}}$) compare to the samples obtained by DC and other PC related samples. Likewise, the corrosion rate (CR) was decreased from 2.126 mil/yr to 3.410 mil/yr for PC 75%, PC-50% and PC-25% duty cycle respectively. This indicates that

at PC-75% duty cycle, good corrosion protecting coatings are achieved.

5.5.2 Electrochemical impedance analysis

Impedance capacities were made using an AC signal with a 5 mV amplitude at OCP in the frequency range of 0.1 Hz to 1 kHz. Spending Z_{Simp} Win 3.21 software, the impedance data was matched to the most appropriate circuit. The Nyquist table was used to calculate impedance parameters.

Fig. 5.6 Nyquist graphs.

Fig. 5.7 Equivalent circuit.

Table 5.4 Corrosion data obtained from Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Temperature	Sample	R_p $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$	C_{dl} (F/cm^2)	CPE Y_0 (F/cm^2)
30 °C	25 %	1720.34	0.0005376	0.0002939
	50 %	1658.97	0.0004008	0.0003512
	75 %	2227.79	0.0002416	0.0003926
	DC	747.11	0.0007283	0.0002153

EIS is a useful technique for the evaluation of the corrosion process at the electrode and electrolyte interface. The higher impedance plots and the greater diameter of the semicircle represent the higher ability to resist corrosion of PC 75% duty cycle coating relative to coatings at other DC and PC duty cycles. Fig. 5.6, shows Nyquist impedance plots of Pt-Rh coatings developed from PC and DC sources. Equivalent circuit diagram is displayed in Fig. 5.7. Where R_p is Polarization resistance, CPE (Constant phase element) and C_{dl} is double-layer capacitance. From Table 5.4, it was noticed that the R_p value was highest for the coatings at 75% duty cycle, thus indicating the good corrosion protection of the coatings at 75% when compared to the rest of the duty cycle and DC source deposition. In addition, the decrease in C_{dl} value with the 75% duty cycle is worth noticing, suggesting a decrease in the double-layer capacitance, which in turn implies a decrease in the corrosion rate. The experimental curve fit precisely with the curve obtained by the electrical equivalent circuit, as shown in Fig. 5.8.

Fig. 5.8 Curve fitting diagram for PC-25% duty cycle.

5.6 Photocatalytic studies

The Pt-Rh coated sample's effect on photocatalytic degradation of MB dye solution was investigated. Methylene blue ($C_{16}H_{18}N_3SCl$) is a cationic heterocyclic aromatic azo-dye whose molecular structure is shown in Fig. 5.9. All trials were carried out in the company of UV light, using a 300W xenon lamp as a light source.

Fig. 5.9 Molecular structure of Methylene Blue

5.6.2 Probable mechanism of dye degradation

The electrons (e^-) in the valence band (VB) excited the conduction band (CB) with the same number of holes (h^+) left in the VB when coated metals were irradiated by photons. Photo generated electrons (e^-) react with O_2 generating O_2^- , while photogenerated h^+ oxidizes MB on the surface of coated Pt-Rh alloy samples. These powerful oxidants could then substantially degrade MB molecules to H_2O , CO_2 , and other molecules of nominal importance. A proposed mechanism for photocatalytic degradation of MB over Pt-Rh alloy coatings was shown in Fig. 5.10. A possible process of photocatalytic degradation of MB over coated metal sample was anticipated as follows:

Fig. 5.10 Proposed mechanism for photocatalytic degradation of MB over Pt-Rh alloy coatings.

5.6.3 Photocatalytic study

The efficiency of degradation has reached 96 % degradation for Pt-Rh coated alloy sample of PC-75% and subsequent dye degradation of remaining duty cycle and DC samples of Pt-Rh is mentioned in Table 5.5 and shown in Fig. 5.11. The dye degradation efficiency of different samples with different concentrations, pH, and scavengers was carried out for 180 minutes with different parameters by selecting the sample with the highest dye degradation from Pt-Rh. We have achieved good degradation for sample coated by PC method in our work, especially at PC-75% duty cycle for Pt-Rh alloy sample compare to DC and other PC samples. This may be due to smaller nanometer grain sizes relative to DC coated samples or other samples. The amount of photons absorbed on its surface is increased by an increase in effluent loading on the catalyst and the OH and e-/h+ pairs are increased. For this purpose, a PC-coated sample with a 75 % duty cycle provides good degradation activities.

Table 5.5 The efficiency of Methylene blue dye degradation by different Pt-Rh alloy samples in the first trial.

Coating source	DC	PC-25%	PC-50%	PC-75%
Degradation %	89	92	94	96

Fig. 5.11 Percentage degradation of MB dye for Pt-Rh coated samples for 5ppm with a run time of 180 minutes.

5.7 Factors affecting dye degradations

5.7.1 Effect of dye concentration

Catalyst action reduced with a rise in the concentration of dye. Degradation of the dye below the light source rest mainly on its concentration. The analysis was carried out in 100 ml over 5 ppm, 10 ppm 15 ppm and 20 ppm dye concentrations to determine the optimum dye concentration as shown in Fig. 5.12 and Table 5.6. This depends on the concentration of dye molecules on the catalytic surface, which in turn lowers the penetration level of light through the catalyst and thus reduces the degradation of the dye. As a result, the rate of generation of hydroxyl radicals and superoxide radicals was found to be lower. 5 ppm result displays more photocatalytic degradation associated with higher dye concentrations. (10–20 ppm).

Fig. 5.12 Photocatalytic activities of MB dye at different dye concentrations with respect to Pt-Rh 75% duty cycle.

Table 5.6 Studies of photocatalytic dye degradation efficiency in terms of different MB dye concentrations.

Coating Source	5 ppm	10 ppm	15 ppm	20 ppm
Pt 75%	96	77	63	51

5.7.2 Effect of pH on dye degradation

pH stands as an important issue that impacts photocatalytic degradation. A 5 ppm MB dye solution was photocatalytically degraded using a Platinum-Rhodium coated sample at 75% duty cycle in pH series extending from 2 to 12. According to Fig. 5.13, photocatalytic activity increases as the pH of the solution increases. In acidic environments, the external surface area of platinum- rhodium covered metal samples is positively charged, while in basic conditions it is negatively charged. Because MB is a cationic dye and Platinum-Rhodium has a negative charge, electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged surface and the cationic MB causes degradation. In the basic medium, the availability of OH⁻ is higher, which speeds up the photocatalytic degradation process. Table 5.7 shows that the Pt-Rh coated sample at 75%

duty cycle has higher dye degradation activities than the other coated samples.

Fig.5.13 Photocatalytic activities of MB dye at different pH with respect Pt-Rh 75% duty cycle.

Table 5.7 Relativereadings of photocatalytic activity of Pt-Rh alloy in terms of different pH.

Coating Source	2 pH	4 pH	6 pH	8 pH	10 pH	12 pH
Pt-Rh 75%	50	61	67	76	83	96

5.7.3 Effect of Temperature

Temperature of the water is around 30 to 50⁰ C in rivers and sea water. Our aim of the work is to carry out the effluent treatment in these types of environments by using this coating as catalyst. During the experiment, temperature of the water is around 40 to 50⁰ C by the source bulb used in the studies. The developed catalyst is more effective in this environment for effluent treatment.

5.7.4 Scavenger studies

Scavenger studies looked into the active agents that cause pollutants to degrade. Under UV light, hydroxide anions, hydrogen ions, electrons, and superoxide anions (oxygen species) form during the photocatalytic degradation process. For the scavenger experiment, tertiary butyl alcohol (TBA) was added to separate dyes for hydroxide anions (OH⁻), EDTA (Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid) for hydrogen ion (H⁺), K₂Cr₂O₇ for electrons, and Ascorbic Acid (AA) for oxygen species such as anion scavengers. The photodegradation of MB dyes catalysed by platinum coated with a 75 % duty cycle under UV light in the presence and absence of scavengers is shown in Fig. 5.14. The most reactive species, hydroxide anion, is found to be the most responsible for MB dye degradation.

Fig. 5.14 Effect of scavengers for Pt-Rh 75% duty cycle on UV light degradation of MB dye at 5ppm.

5.7.5 Reusability and stability of MB dye

Stability and regaining are the foremost worries concerning photocatalytic degradation in Platinum-Rhodium electrodeposition. After degradation (cycle 1) Platinum-rhodium-coated samples were washed with distilled water to remove adsorbed dye molecules on the surface of the photocatalyst, trailed by drying in the oven to remove water molecules. The recovery and stability testing was accompanied using dried samples over four consecutive cycles of

degradation. Subsequently, four cycles, the reusability efficiency of the photocatalyst decreased from 97 % (1st cycle) to 85 % (4th cycle) as shown in Fig. 5.15. Photocatalyst activity decreased efficiency by 12 % even after the 4th cycle of degradation. Recycled catalysts can be used for further degradation of dye under visible light sources [27].

Fig. 5.15 The stability of the MB dye in the Pt-Rh coated sample over various cycles.

5.7.6 Reusability and Stability of Methyl orange and Rhodamine – B

Initially, dye degradation was performed with three different organic dyes: MB, methyl orange, and Rhodamine B. (RhB). Good efficiency was noted for MB dye with a 97 % degradation rate for PC 75 %, but maximum efficiency for methyl orange and RhB reduced to 92 % and 90 %, respectively. As a result, we're interested in MB for photodegradation using Pt-Rh coated electrodeposition samples. When the MB dye's reusability and stability were tested, just a decline in 3% efficiency was found.

Similarly, reusability and stability were examined for methyl orange and RhB dye. It was understood that cyclability was decreased from 92% to 73%, Fig. 5.16 (a) and 90% to 77%, Fig. 5.16 (b) for methyl orange and RhB respectively after four cycles. From this obtained evidence we were concluded that in our research report, MB dye shows better

photodegradation activities along with reusability and stability, whereas methyl orange and RhB dye performance decreases in dye degradation as well as in reusability.

Fig. 5.16 The reusability and stability of the (a) methyl orange and (b) RhB dye in the Pt-Rh coated sample over various cycles.

5.8 Conclusions

This invention involves the field of electrodeposition of metals. More precisely, it relates to the process of obtaining platinum-rhodium alloy coating by both DC and PC methods and it is distinguished by SEM and XRD. EDX study confirms the Pt and Rh presence in the coating and their contribution towards corrosion resistance and photocatalytic properties. From the data of XRD, we came up with the conclusion that 75% of PC samples reduced the crystalline size more compare to the remaining PCs and DC samples. Finest corrosion resistance coating was developed for the PC-75% duty cycle. For Methylene blue dye, which is present in the textile industries, Pt-Rh exhibits higher photodegradation and has a great potential application in wastewater treatment. All in all, one day electrodeposited Pt-Rh alloy-coated samples will replace the existing methods which are suitable for waste management, water disinfection.

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CHAPTER – 6

**Application in hydrogen
generation:**

**Platinum - Rhodium alloy
electrodeposition**

6.1 Introduction

Techniques for exploiting promising clean, renewable energy sources need to be established due to the depletion of traditional fossil fuels and the gradual degradation of the environment. Due to its excellent theoretical mass-energy density (120 mj kg^{-1}) and zero greenhouse emissions, hydrogen is a highly efficient and environmental friendly energy medium [1-3]. Hydrogen can be generated by water electrolysis efficiently electrochemically using catalysts with long-term stability. It is necessary to enable large-scale practical applications that are affordable. Platinum is the best catalyst for HER because of high activity with zero overpotential [4]. But, platinum is costly (\$988 per ounce) and low abundant makes it difficult to use in large scale HER process [5-7]

Recently, a large amount of research work has been carried out to develop alternatives to platinum catalysts. In this direction, catalysts based on molybdenum, nickel, cobalt, Molybdenum oxides, sulfides, selenides compounds have been explored [8-12]. These catalysts show quite good HER activity in an acidic medium. However, these catalysts do not compete with Pt in terms of overpotential and current densities. In addition, the preparation of these compounds is highly complex and environmentally unfriendly.

Despite numerous efforts, only 4% of H_2 was produced by water electrolysis due to the high cost of the process [13]. These all are due to the high energy losses in electrolysis, lack of state-of-the-art electrodes, the key barriers to the wider use of water electrolysis.

Platinum is the best catalyst for hydrogen generation because it is having zero overpotential. The only hindrance of using noble metals and their alloys is low abundance and costly. Using of bulk noble metal is not favorable to use in hydrogen generation. Catalytic activities mainly depend on the surface properties and by using this principle, a thin layer of noble metal and its alloy coating on base metal usage as a catalyst is a good alternative and cost-effective method in hydrogen generation. Pt-Rh alloy coating is more durable and superior than pure platinum coatings [14]. Qiao Yan et al developed the Pt-Rh alloy for degradation of 4-nitrophenol and rhodamine B [15]. Another study used a simple one-pot solvothermal strategy to efficiently prepare bimetallic Pt-Rh alloyed dendritic nano assemblies (DNAs) for generation of hydrogen [16]. Pt-Rh nano assemblies (NAs) prepared under solvothermal conditions given a good hydrogen generation [17]. Pt-Rh alloy nano dendrites as an advanced electrocatalyst for ethylene glycol oxidation and hydrogen evolution reactions [18]. Pt-Rh coating is the best option on boiler water reactors because of neutron activation considerations. Alloying of Pt with Rh is another method to achieve lower overpotential with

higher efficiency in hydrogen generation. Noble metal nanomaterials (e.g., Pt, Au, Ag, Rh, and Pd) have been extensively researched for their possible future industrial applications in fuel cells [19], catalysis [20, 21] and sensing devices [22]. Especially Pt – Rh alloy is a very good catalyst for hydrogen evolution [23]. [In this work Pt-Rh coating was developed on SS 304 with a very small amount of $0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ noble metal. The Pt-Rh coatings were performed by both DC and PC methods at different conditions. These developed coatings are characterized by SEM, XRD, AFM and studied by electrochemical methods to know the efficiency of hydrogen generation. The Pt-Rh catalysts display Pt like behaviour for the HER process in an acidic medium. The PC coated Pt-Rh coating outperforms compared to the DC coated samples.

6.2 Materials and method

6.2.1 Electrodeposition Process

Platinum 5Q plating solution $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{HPO}_4$ and Rhodium Sulphate solution $\text{Rh}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ purchased from Arora Matthey Limited, Kolkata was used as the main content in the electrolyte for the Electrodeposition process. 1.5 ml Platinum solution and 0.075 ml of Rhodium solution from the 5Q plating solution was taken to prepare the electrolyte solution. This solution is marked to 50 ml by adding 5 ml $\text{ConcH}_2\text{SO}_4$ and distilled water. A Pt-Rh alloy coating was developed on SS 304 with an exposed surface area of 1.7 cm^2 from a bath solution containing 50 ml. The anode and cathode were held parallel to each other during Electrodeposition. To achieve a smooth finish, stainless steel panels are manually polished, cleaned ultrasonically then electrochemically cleaned before electroplating.

The SS 304 circular form cathode with a diameter of 15 mm and a thickness of 1 mm was used during electrodeposition for coating with a total surface area of 1.7 cm^2 , while the remaining portion of the backside was masked during the deposition process. Platinized titanium was used as an anode. Electrodeposition was carried out by using a current source N6705B Key sight of direct current (DC) and pulse current (PC) for 18 minutes. After each deposition, the coatings obtained were rinsed carefully with distilled water and then air-dried. The amount of coating was estimated by weighing the cathode before and after coating.

6.2.2 Coatings characterization

The morphology analysis of coated samples was conducted by scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) (ZEISS sigma) after electroplating. SEM assessment explored the surface morphology and porosity of DC and PC coating on SS304. Platinum-coated samples were mounted on a sample holder and SEM photographs were taken using a 5.00 kV and 15 kV

(model: FESEM Carl ZEISS) scanning electron microscope, 3.7 mm average wide distance at varying magnification. The EDX analysis (using 20 keV beam energy Model: Oxford Instrument 250). X-ray diffraction (Rigaku Miniflex 600 (5th gen)) was used to obtain X-ray diffractometer patterns. Atomic force microscopic tests (Nanosurf® EasyScan 2 AFM & STM) have shown the surface morphologies of coated samples have been reported to support the findings of other experimental methods. AFM micrographs have shown surface morphological characteristics for both coated samples and bare as a reference.

6.2.3 Electrochemical studies

The electrochemical cell was designed for quantitative measurement of hydrogen, where the electrodeposited Pt-Rh electrode was subjected to cathodic polarization, respectively. Electrodeposited alloy coatings obtained under different deposition conditions were used as the test electrode and platinum electrode with the high surface area was used as the counter electrode. A saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as the reference electrode. All potentials reported in the present study are concerning SCE and converted to a standard hydrogen electrode (SHE)

Electrochemical behaviour of the coatings, in terms of HER, was evaluated by subjecting it to cyclic voltammetry, linear sweep voltammetry and chronopotentiometry studies in 0.5M H₂SO₄ medium, using computer-controlled using an electrochemical workstation (compactostat.h 10800 from Ivium Technologies, Netherlands). The cell was fitted with a graduated gas collector where the liberated hydrogen replaces the corresponding amount of solution. This facility allows relating the amount of gas liberated at a given time for electrode materials deposited at a given current density. The schematic diagram of the setup is given in Fig. 6.1.

Fig. 6.1 Tubular three-electrode glass cell used to measure the electrocatalytic activity of the platinum-rhodium metal alloy electrodeposit in terms of H₂ released on the surface of the electrode.

6.3 Results and Discussions

To get a good desirable coating, bath parameters like pH, temperature, current density, and composition plays a very important role in the coating. Optimized bath conditions are given in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1 Optimized constituent's bath solution

Components	Composition
Platinum solution [Pt (NH ₃) ₂] HPO ₄	1.5 ml
Rhodium sulphate solution Rh ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	0.075 ml
H ₂ SO ₄	5 ml
Distilled water	43.425
Electrodeposition Parameter	
Temperature	40°C
pH	1.0
Current density	4.0 A/dm ²
Deposition time	18 min
PC Duty cycle	25%, 50% and 75%
DC	Direct current flow

6.4 Coatings Characterizations

6.4.1 Scanning electron microscope

SEM images of the coatings obtained from the PC and DC method are shown in Fig. 6.2 The 75% duty cycle coating exhibited the smaller and uniform grains result in a smoother coating surface compared to remaining coatings. In 75% PC coating we have observed more pores with uniform size. In other coatings, pores size was uneven. The degree of uniformity decreased as duty cycle percentage decreases the value from 75% to 25% while pore with larger and uneven size has been observed in DC coating samples. As observed in the figures, the duty cycle has a significant effect on the surface morphology. All these coatings were highly adhesion and bright. The 75% duty cycle sample showed more uniformity than other coatings.

Fig. 6.2 Surface morphology of Pt-Rh coating produced at different conditions. (a) DC (b) PC 25% (c) PC 50%, (d) PC 75%

6.4.2 X-ray diffraction (XRD)

Fig. 6.3 The Pt-Rh coating XRD pattern obtained at DC and PC (25%, 50% and 75%).

The XRD patterns Pt-Rh coating electrodeposition on stainless steel surface by DC and PC (25%, 50% and 75%) technique are displayed as shown in Fig. 6.3. The peaks of XRD pattern were analyzed by using crystallographic search match software using powder diffraction files PDF numbers: 70-2057 Pt, 65-7007 Fe 9.7 Pt 0.3 and 23-298 Fe, C. The X-ray diffraction peaks include Pt (111) peak and an iron rich platinum phase (110) Fe_{9.7}Pt_{0.3} and these phases also contain small amount of Rh. The other peaks at Fe, C (111), Fe, C (200), Fe, C (220) are due to base metal steel.

6.4.3 Atomic Force Microscopy

Fig. 6.4 (a) (b) (c) and (d) is the 3D figures representing the platinum-rhodium coating roughness of DC, PC at 25%, 50% and 75% duty cycle respectively.

Table 6.2 Presents the surface topography of DC and PC electrodeposition of platinum-rhodium alloy coating.

Specimen	Mean (S_m) (fm)	Valley depth (S_v) (nm)	Peak height (S_p) (nm)	Peak valley height (S_y) (nm)	Average roughness (S_a) (nm)	Root mean square roughness (S_q) (nm)
DC	-2872.2am	-109.83	75.786	185.62	14.637	19.572
25	-2872.1am	-222.63	138.97	361.6	23.748	31.734
50	-4.2823fm	-70.167	48.551	118.72	10.831	13.669
75	-4.9253fm	-61.429	141.88	203.31	7.6879	11.184

AFM is an important instrument for studying the surface morphology at nano-to-microscale and has become a modern approach for studying the effect of the different electrodeposition methods like DC and PC at various duty cycles. AFM research includes details on average roughness (S_a) on the surface of coated SS304 sample, which helps to assess the effectiveness of the coated sample by electrodeposition method as shown in Table 6.2. The 3D images of Pt-Rh alloy coating for DC, 25%, 50% and 75% duty cycle are shown in Fig. 6.4 (a) to 6.4 (d). A sample obtained by 75% duty cycle by PC method showed lesser roughness than other coatings which indicates Pt-Rh is deposited quite uniformly. The decrease in roughness value (Table 6.2 and Fig. 6.4 (a)) is due to the reduction of the grain size on the metal (SS 304) surface. It can be concluded that the higher the crystal grain size, the greater the roughness of the coatings. The instability of the duty cycle has a significant effect on the surface morphology of their crystalline measurements. In our studies, the good coating was achieved in a 75% duty cycle and it gives a smaller grain size with lower roughness. In DC coating, sufficient time was not available to achieve the small grain size with a uniform coating.

6.4.4 Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy

The EDX analysis was performed to measure the number of metal ions on the substrate in the coating and offers valuable information on the percentage of specific metal ions in the coating. Details are given in Table 6.4.4.2 and Fig. 6.5. In the course of our studies, EDX were observed for both DC and PC techniques. It also contains trace amounts of iron, chromium, nickel and manganese. It shows more amount of iron along with Platinum and Rhodium it may be due to porosity in the coating as shown in Figure 6.4.1.1.

Fig. 6.4.4.1 Designates the presence of Pt and Rh in its alloy coating by EDX technique.

Amount of Platinum – Rhodium Alloy in the coating

Pt-Rh coating was done by the PC and DC method. The weight of the cathode coupons was taken before and after the experiments. The Amount of alloy in the coating was given in Table 6.3.

Table 6.3 Amount of Pt-Rh alloy in the coating

SI NO	Method of coating	Amount of Pt-Rh deposited after coating ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)
01	DC	10
02	PC 25%	07
03	PC 50%	06
04	PC 75%	05

6.5 Electrocatalytic activity of HER

6.5.1 Linear Sweep voltammetry

The electrocatalytic activity of Pt-Rh was first evaluated for H_2 evolution in an acidic medium as shown in Fig. 6.6. All the samples show a good hydrogen evolution reaction. Pt – Rh coated by PC method at 75% duty cycle shows very low overpotential for hydrogen evolution. Pt-Rh catalyst deposited by 75% duty cycle sample shows overpotential similar to that of pure Pt for HER. The Pt-Rh sample shows $0.55 \text{ A}/\text{cm}^2$ current. These results confirm the better performance of the sample (75% duty cycle). 25% and 50% sample shows more overpotential and also less current observed during hydrogen evolution reaction. It was anticipated that Pt–Rh is very active for HER. Indeed, the Pt–Rh catalyst exhibited a catalytic onset at nearly zero overpotential and catalytic current rapidly rose for the sample obtained at 75% duty cycle. Vibrant H_2 bubble growth and release from the surface were observed upon further cathodic sweeping.

Fig. 6.6 LSV curves for HER on the surface of the Platinum-Rhodium coatings

Table 6.4 The Tafel slopes obtained for the different Pt-Rh electrodes

Si No	Pt-Rh electrode sample	Slope Value mV/dec
01	Pure platinum	36.0
02	DC	69.6
03	PC- 75%	41.2
04	PC- 50%	63.6
05	PC- 25%	83.1

Fig. 6.7 Tafel plots for various electrodes in 0.5 M H₂SO₄

The catalytic activity of Pt-Rh electrocatalysts was evaluated by Tafel plots as shown in Fig. 6.7. The Tafel slopes provide insight into the mechanism of the HER process. The kinetics parameter of electrocatalytic HER is expressed in terms of either Volmer-Heyrovsky or Volmer-Tafel mechanistic pathways. The Tafel slopes of 41.2, 63.6 and 83.1 mV/dec for Pt-Rh catalysts coated by PC method using 75%, 50% and 25% duty cycles, respectively from Table 6.4. Very low Tafel slope of 41.2 mV/dec of 75% duty cycle deposited Pt-Rh catalysts implies that better electrocatalytic performance which is also higher than the DC coated sample (69.9 mV/dec). The low Tafel slope of 41.2 mV/dec implies that the Volmer-Tafel reaction mechanism and the rate-determining step is the desorption of hydrogen atoms [24].

6.5.2 Chronopotentiometry

Fig. 6.8 Chronopotentiometry curves measured in 0.5M H₂SO₄ at a current density of 4.0 A/cm²

The simplest way to estimate the electrocatalytic activity of the electrodes to monitor the electrode potential at constant current density is applied over a sufficient period [25]. The chronopotentiometry study for the evolution of hydrogen on Pt-Rh coatings obtained by different methods was made at a constant current of -0.3 mA cm^{-2} for a duration of 21,600 seconds. The nature of chrono-potentiostats for the alloy coatings obtained by different methods is given in Fig. 6.8. The electrocatalytic performance of these coatings was evaluated by measuring the amount of H₂ liberated in the first 150 seconds as shown in Fig. 6.9. The electrodeposited catalysts show constant and stabilized potential for HER. This phenomenon is ascribed to the formation of hydrogen bubbles on the surface of the electrode. Coating with uniform grain size and porosity gives more hydrogen evolution reaction. In electrolysis, formed hydrogen gas detached from the cathode only after it became bigger in size. During this time contact between cathode and electrolyte was seized and reduces the hydrogen evolution. If the sample has more uniform pores, these gas bubbles avoid the ohmic

resistance and enhance the catalytic activity of the coating [26]. It may be seen that the coating obtained by 75% duty cycle gives more volume of hydrogen evolution compare to other samples. This sample has more porosity with a uniform coating this enhance the hydrogen generation activity of the catalyst.

Fig. 6.9 Volume of H₂ evolved in 150 seconds on each test electrodes are shown here.

6.6 Conclusions

Pt- Rh Alloy Coating was successfully done by the PC and DC method. Both parameters were optimized to get the desired coating. SEM and XRD infers the smaller grain size of the coating obtained by the PC method at 75% duty cycle. EDX confirms the presence of Pt and Rh on the substrate. AFM analysis showcases the surface roughness and this is confirmed the SEM results. Linear sweep voltammetry gives the evidence of zero over the potential of developed alloy coating and also it gave more current than pure platinum coating. Small Tafel slopes confirm the efficient catalysts and follow the Volmer-Tafel reaction mechanism for the HER. Chronopotentiometry values again confirm overall results by giving more volume of hydrogen collection during electrolysis. This work has the potential to commercialize for industrial applications.

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CHAPTER – 7

**Summary and scope for the future
work**

SUMMARY OF THE RESEARCH WORK

In our study, Platinum, Rhodium and Platinum Rhodium alloy were coated on SS304 by Electrodeposition method. In our work, around 1 micron thickness coating with around 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of noble metal, was coated on steel. It reduced the overall cost of the raw materials. These coatings are used as catalyst for hydrogen generation, antibacterial studies, dye degradation and corrosion studies.

We have coated noble metals by DC and PC method with small amount by reducing cost effect to give more applications. These coatings are characterised by SEM, XRD and AFM. All these coatings were subjected for different applications. These coatings give similar results like pure noble metals.

In this research work, platinum group metals such as platinum, rhodium, and platinum-rhodium alloy coatings were generated by the electrodeposition method by adopting DC and PC techniques. The main intention of the work is to generate the coating in a short period of time at a low temperature, without the additives, levellers, and organic agents in order to get bright, uniform, and uneven coatings. All the variables such as composition of the bath, pH, temperature, concentration, duration and current density were optimized in direct and pulse electrodeposition methods.

We prefer PC to DC for coating noble metals because DC electroplating consumes a large number of metal ions from the bath solution, resulting in poor coating. The PC plating process, on the other hand, would have been tremendously useful in terms of reducing the amount of noble metals consumed during plating, which might have had a range of industrial uses, as we studied in our research. Consequently, manufacturing costs will be reduced, production times will be reduced, and coating quality will improve. Furthermore, just one parameter, the current density, may be altered in traditional DC plating. The PC approach, on the other hand, offers three key features: peak current density, current ON time, and current OFF time can all be adjusted, and growth can be managed.

The thesis comprises seven chapters are as follows

Chapter 1 will give a general introduction to noble metals and properties of PGM's and an introduction to electrodeposition and its types. The basic concept of the different applications carried out in the research: are corrosion and its mitigation; dye degradation by photocatalytic method, its source; various dyes and their effects on the environment; introduction to hydrogen and its production; and antibacterial study using noble metals. Finally, this chapter explains the detailed literature survey and provides a brief summary of the work.

Chapter 2 describes the materials and experimental methods used throughout the study. It includes the introduction of substrate SS304 and its pre-treatment procedure, the experimental part of electrodeposition and bath optimization. It also presents the principles and instrument details of various characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction analysis, Scanning electron microscopy, Energy Dispersity X-ray spectroscopy, Atomic force microscopy and UV-Visible Spectrophotometer. This chapter also covers the principles involved in photocatalytic dye degradation, antibacterial research, and the hydrogen evolution reaction.

Chapter 3 describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings, applications in photocatalytic dye degradation mechanisms under UV irradiation and investigation of factors affecting the dye degradation process.

Chapter 4 this paper describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings and electrocatalytic performance of HER by linear sweep voltammetry, chronopotentiometry and Tafel measurements.

Chapter 5 covers the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum-rhodium alloy electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings, corrosion rate measurements by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, applications in photocatalytic dye degradation consisting of its mechanisms, and investigation of factors affecting the dye degradation process.

Chapter 6: this paper describes the pretreatment of substrate SS304, bath optimization for platinum electrodeposition, characterization of the coatings and electrocatalytic performance of HER by linear sweep voltammetry, chronopotentiometry, and Tafel measurements.

Chapter 7: Summarizes the results obtained in the present investigation and the scope for the future work.

SCOPE FOR THE FUTURE WORK

- Grain size, coating stability, throwing power, durability, and reduced thickness are some of the areas where future study could be focused.
- Hydrogen generation via the water splitting process may be scaled up to a low-cost synthesis technique for large quantities and photocatalytic dye degradation with various organic dyes can be examined.
- To combat bacterial growth, antibacterial investigations using additional noble metals, alloy and metal composites can be conducted.
- Innovative methods that have been tried and tested in the industrial business may be included in future study.
- Young researchers, scientists, and faculty members might also intend to use similar methodologies to acquire a better understanding of the progress and benefits of these proposed applications on a big scale industrial level.
- All this will assist in the simplification, economic development, and greening of the environment.

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4. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen, V.S. Tripathi, G. Nagaraju, D.H. Nagaraju, K.O. Nayana. Highly Corrosion Resistant Platinum-Rhodium alloy coating and its photocatalytic activity. Inorganic Chemistry Communications, 134 109065 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2021.109065> (**Impact Factor- 2.495**)
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6. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen, V.S. Tripathi, The development of platinum-rhodium alloy coatings on SS304 using a pulse/direct electrodeposition technique, and their application to antibacterial activity. Journal of the Indian Chemical Society. 99 (6) 2022, 100466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jics.2022.100466> (**Impact Factor- 0.284**)

7. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen, V.S. Tripathi, Chethana M and Prashanth Kumar H.P. Development of Pulse/Direct electrodeposition, characterization, and antibacterial activity of platinum coatings on SS304, Materials Today Communications (**Communicated**)

8. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen, V.S. Tripathi, D.H. Nagaraju. Advanced Strategies for Hydrogen Generation by Rhodium Metal Catalysts Coated by the Electrodeposition Method. Inorganic Chemistry Communications. (**Under review**)

9. **Bharath K. Devendra**, B.M. Praveen, V.S. Tripathi, G. Nagaraju, Prasanna B.M, Shashank M. Development of Rhodium coatings by Electrodeposition for Photocatalytic Dye Vacuum. (**Under Review**)

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A Review on Noble Metals in Controlling Intergranular Stress Corrosion Cracking in BWRs

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Hydrogen Evolution Reaction by Platinum Coating

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Abstract

A thin layer of platinum coating ($0.5 \mu\text{gcm}^{-2}$) on stainless steel surface was deposited by direct current (DC) and pulse current (PC) electrodeposition method for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) application. Scanning electron microscopy, atomic force microscopy, and X-ray diffraction analysis were used to characterize the coatings. Linear sweep voltammetry and cyclic voltammetry studies were carried out to know the overpotential values for hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) on these coatings. The optimization of catalytic activity for hydrogen evolution using different coating methods helps in reducing the overall cost. Tafel polarization experiments were conducted for DC and PC platinum coating to know hydrogen generation trend. Cathodic slope and HER current values revealed that, coatings obtained at 75% duty cycle by PC method exhibit lower cathodic slope, high current density of 150 mA/cm^2 and more corrosion current with highest hydrogen evolution. Chronopotentiometry experiments showed that 20 ml of hydrogen was collected from 75% sample.

Keywords Electrodeposition · Platinum · HER · LSV · Chronopotentiometry

1 Introduction

Despite being one of the fastest electrocatalytic reactions, the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) requires high platinum loadings ($0.5\text{--}1.0 \text{ mg/cm}^2$). It requires optimization of the extent of catalyst loading in order to reduce the cost of the electrode. Redox reactions at electrode and solution interfaces are becoming increasingly important in modern science and technology, as they decide the efficiency of a variety of electrochemical devices to be used in the future for sustainable renewable energy (Ahmed et al. 2017; Aliaksandr Bandarenka and Koper 2013; Bicakova and Straka 2012; Carmo et al. 2013; El-Shobaky et al.

1997). Efficiencies of electrolyzers and fuel cells are mainly determined by the effectiveness of the interface between catalytic electrodes and electrolytes (Holewinski et al. 2013; Hussain et al. 2018; Jakub et al. 2016; Jeong Eun et al. 2020; Jeong Eun et al. 2016; Koper 2011). However, by using the latest technology and art, only around 4% of hydrogen is produced from water electrolysis (Mohsen et al. 2019; Mokhtar et al. 2001; Muralikrishna et al. 2015). It is mainly due to the lack of design of the electrodes that leads to less production of hydrogen with high over voltage leading to high energy loss. In producing 15 trillion moles of hydrogen per year (4%), the average price is EUR 0.1kWh in the US and Europe (Nagi Radwan et al. 2003; Norskov et al. 2009; Stephensfan et al. 2012). These costs of production are higher than that for the production of hydrogen using noble metals as catalysts. By using the proper knowledge in noble metal coating, the production of hydrogen is an economically viable method (Subbaraman et al. 2011; Symes Mark and Cronin 2013). The amount of platinum on the coating is a very important parameter, and by using proper knowledge, a small amount platinum in the coating reduces the cost-effective and gives the highest amount of hydrogen gas.

In this proposed work, platinum metal was coated by DC and PC method with a minimum load of $0.5 \mu\text{g/cm}^2$. All these deposits were analyzed by SEM, AFM and XRD.

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Pt–Rh alloy catalysts for hydrogen generation developed by direct current/pulse current method

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Abstract

Highly active Pt–Rh alloy catalyst coatings were developed by direct current (DC) and pulse current (PC) electrodeposition method for efficient hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) catalysts. The coatings were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), X-ray diffraction (XRD), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) studies. Pt–Rh alloy catalyst coatings showed almost similar behaviour as pure platinum metal. The Pt–Rh coating was obtained by the PC method showing low overpotential for HER. A very low slope of 41.2 mV/dec obtained represents the Volmer–Tafel mechanistic pathway for the HER process. Chronopotentiometry was conducted, and the amount of hydrogen collected during these experiments was 24 ml for the PC method 75% duty cycle sample.

Keywords Electrodeposition · Platinum–rhodium alloy · HER · CV · Chronopotentiometry

Introduction

Techniques for exploiting promising clean, renewable energy sources need to be established due to the depletion of traditional fossil fuels and the gradual degradation of the environment. Due to its excellent theoretical mass energy density (120 mJ kg⁻¹) and zero greenhouse emissions, hydrogen is a highly efficient and environmental friendly energy medium [1–3]. Hydrogen can be generated by water electrolysis efficiently electrochemically using catalysts with long-term stability. It is necessary to enable large-scale practical applications that are affordable. Platinum is the best catalyst for HER because of high activity with zero overpotential [4].

But, platinum is costly (\$988 per ounce) and low abundant makes it difficult to use in large-scale HER process [5–7].

Recently, a large amount of research work has been carried out to develop alternatives to platinum catalysts. In this direction, catalysts based on molybdenum, nickel, cobalt, molybdenum oxides, sulphides and selenides compounds have been explored [8–12]. These catalysts show quite good HER activity in an acidic medium. However, these catalysts do not compete with Pt in terms of overpotential and current densities. In addition, the preparation of these compounds is highly complex and environmentally unfriendly.

Despite numerous efforts, only 4% of H₂ was produced by water electrolysis due to the high cost of the process [13]. These all are due to the high energy losses in electrolysis and lack of state-of-the-art electrodes, the key barriers to the wider use of water electrolysis.

Platinum is the best catalyst for hydrogen generation because it is having zero overpotential. The only hindrance of using noble metals and their alloys is low abundance and high cost. Using of bulk noble metal is not favourable to use in hydrogen generation. Catalytic activities mainly depend on the surface properties, and by using this principle, a thin layer of noble metal and its alloy coating on base metal usage as a catalyst is a good alternative and cost-effective method in hydrogen generation. Pt–Rh alloy coating is more durable and superior than pure platinum coatings [14]. Qiao

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Highly corrosion resistant platinum-rhodium alloy coating and its photocatalytic activity

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ABSTRACT

A method of electroplating a platinum–rhodium (Pt–Rh) alloy coating with a specified composition on a metal substrate stainless steel (SS304) is presented in this article. The Pt–Rh bath consists of [Pt (NH₃)₂]HPO₄, H₂SO₄ and Rh₂(SO₄)₃. The Pt–Rh alloy electrodeposition coatings were characterized by different analytical methods such as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). SEM images justify that coating is uniform in a 75% duty cycle. Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX) confirms the presence of Pt and Rh in the coating. XRD confirms that crystalline size was reduced from 75% duty cycle to the rest of the PC's coatings and DC (Direct current). The incorporation of the Pt–Rh metal ions was verified by EDX analyses. The corrosion behaviour of the developed Pt–Rh alloy coatings was evaluated in 0.1 M Na₂SO₄ solution using potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance techniques. The coating developed at PC-75% duty cycle possesses the highest corrosion resistance. A photocatalytic degradation study of Pt–Rh coating was conducted for Methylene Blue (MB) dyes under UV light radiation. The dye removal efficiency of Pt–Rh coated samples was 97% after irradiation and PC 75% duty cycles showed an exceptional dye degradation percentage compare to the DC coating source. All photocatalytic behaviour was controlled by using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer.

1. Introduction

Platinum, palladium, rhodium, ruthenium, iridium, and osmium are members of the platinum group metals (PGM). Only platinum, palladium, and rhodium have previously found significant use in the electrodeposited condition [1]. The main disadvantage of this alloy coating is its high cost; however, its benefits include excellent chemical and oxidation resistance, as well as high strength, the main resistance to corrosion at high temperatures, are present in different areas such as the production of glass [2,3] and nitrogen fertilizers [4,5,6], thermocouples [7], automotive catalysts [8], jewellery [9,10] etc.

Pulse Electrodeposition is considered a more efficient method of Electroplating compare to the DC method of Electrodeposition. In the PC method, based on the required current can be controlled by the ON and OFF method. In ON time current is passed into the time it is switched off. During OFF time more time will be given to nucleation and which reduces the nuclei size and give the uniform crystalline size. We value PC

over DC in Pt–Rh alloy coating because electroplating of Pt–Rh by DC consumes a major amount of metal ions from the bath solution, resulting in the poor coating. The PC plating technique, on the other hand, would be extremely beneficial in that have noticeably reduced the amount of Pt–Rh consumed during plating which may find various industrial applications. As a result, production costs will be lower, production time will be shorter, and coating quality will improve [11]. Also, conventionally DC plating only one parameter, namely, the current density can be varied. However, the PC method has three important factors: peak current density, current ON time and current OFF time can be varied and growth can be controlled [12].

Noble metal coatings were done on stainless steel to control the corrosion in boiler water reactors. Intergranular corrosion is very common in boilers. So the development of noble metal coatings on stainless steel with high corrosion resistance is very important in boilers. Noble metal chemical addition is a recent development in this field and it reduces corrosion abruptly. Many methods are available to coat noble

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Platinum Coatings on SS304: Photocatalytic Dye Degradation Application

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Abstract

This article successfully explains the coating of platinum on stainless steel sample (SS304) by simple direct current electrodeposition (DC) and pulse current electrodeposition (PC) method. All parameters of operation like current density, temperature, duty cycle and pH were optimized. Various analysis techniques were used to categorize the platinum deposited sample, including electron dispersive spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy. Platinum-coated samples show excellent photocatalytic activity towards methylene blue. PC-coated sample shows better dye degradation performance than DC-coated sample which was monitored by using UV–Vis spectrophotometer.

Keywords Chronoamperometry · Dye degradation · Electrodeposition · Nucleation · Noble metal

1 Introduction

More than 150 years earlier, Elkington, who received a patent in 1837 (Parker 1959) and later Bijtger, developed the first experiments on the electrolytic deposition of platinum group metals (Bottger 1878). There has been a substantial increase in the supply of chemical and electrochemical deposition methods for platinum metals, especially for platinum as illustrated by recent literature (Rao and Trivedi 2005; Rao and Pushpavanam 2001; Johnson Matthey Technology Division 1992). In solar panels, fuel cells, boiler reactors etc., platinum group

metals are used more advantageously as strong catalysts. Because of their relative inertness, ability to catalyze complex chemical reactions, and biocompatibility, noble metals are extensively utilized in commercial applications. It's also non-toxic and non-explosive, which is an added plus. Low tension, brilliant, adhesive, and uniform deposition are required for this system (Baumgärtner and Raub 1988; Sathasivam et al. 2017; Marco et al. 2016). Due to their high cost, bulk metals are frequently replaced with a thin layer of metal deposited on less expensive electrode supports (Ghaemi and Binder 2002). These applications require a different type of morphology and structure. Production of such coating for various applications with nano- and micro-size is a great challenge (Marlot et al. 2002; Yin et al. 1977).

The electrodeposition method is considered a simple, efficient, effective and economical method to produce a noble metal coating. It is obtained in a simple metal salt solution for a small duration. Platinum is a very expensive metal, and the electrodeposition method gives very thin and adherent coating in small duration for various applications (Yoshimura et al. 1986; Fukumoto et al. 1984; Kollia et al. 1991). In this method, by varying the bath parameters we can achieve the different grain sizes from nano-size to micro-size, thickness, porosity and adhesion properties (Chatzisyseon et al. 2009; Fierro and Cominellis 2010; Santos et al. 2013). Nowadays PC

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The development of platinum-rhodium alloy coatings on SS304 using a pulse/direct electrodeposition technique and their application to antibacterial activity

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ABSTRACT

The current research focused on the development of Platinum-Rhodium alloy coating (Pt-Rh) on SS304 and its applications in antibacterial studies. Electrodeposition is considered to be one of the most suitable methods because it enhances the therapeutic effects of noble metals (Pt-Rh alloy). The electrodeposited coating is an economical and time-saving alternative to existing coating methods. The newly developed Pt-Rh coating was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and an atomic force microscope (AFM). Using the agar Petri plate and broth culture method, the antibacterial effect of the platinum-rhodium alloy was investigated against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus saprophytes*, *Bacillus Subtilis*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*. The Pt-Rh alloy coated samples obtained by Direct current (DC) and Pulse coating (PC 50% and PC 75%) were examined for antibacterial study. The PC 75% Pt-Rh alloy coating exhibits significant antibacterial activity, demonstrating a maximum zone of inhibition while leaving the rest of the coated samples by DC and PC 50% duty cycles. The study also found that when the concentration of Pt-Rh solution rises from 5 μ L to 15 μ L, so does the antibacterial activity. The findings of the study showed that electrodeposited platinum-rhodium alloy metal ions may be handy bacteriostatic in the coming years.

1. Introduction

Antimicrobial action is already used in a wide range of industries, such as textile materials, water chlorination, pharmaceuticals, and packaged food. Organic detergents, on the other side, have some disadvantages, including toxicity to humans and antibiotic resistance [1]. Metals were once thought to be useful in the treatment of diseases [2–5]. Because of metal Nanoparticles, metal oxide, metal oxides doped with ions, metal ions, and metal salts consistency, reliability, long life cycle, and safety, metals ions have gotten a lot of attention in recent decades. Noble metals have distinctive electronic and optical properties, trying to make them promising antimicrobial channels [6]. As a result, nowadays current research focuses on noble metals such as Au, Ag, Pt, Pd, and Ru, as well as their alloys [7–11]. The noble metals which are named under PGMs (Ir, Os, Pd, Pt, Rh, and Ru) have similar physical and chemical

properties, in addition to a greater propensity for being found in the same mineral ores reserves. Platinum-group metals have dual anticancer and antibacterial properties. PGMs in sandwich and half-sandwich form improve antibacterial and anticancer activity [12–15]. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (Ag-NPs) using *Camellia sinensis* [16] and palladium nanoparticles (Pd-NPs) [17] demonstrated maximum inhibition for gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Using Pt-Pd nanoparticles (Pt-Pd NPs), an environmentally friendly method for photodegrading hazardous contaminants from wastewater and antioxidant, antibacterial and lipid peroxidation inhibition applications has been developed [18]. The antibacterial effect was also conducted on nanoparticle synthesis by using noble Ag metal with the *Arum italicum* plant [19]. Around twenty-eight rhodium complexes were evaluated for their antibacterial and antifungal studies [20,21]. Single and combined antimicrobial efficacies for nine metal ion solutions including rhodium

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